

WP2

D2.1 Co-creation methodology

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¹ PU = Public
SEN: Sensitive

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GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

AB: Advisory Board

D: Deliverable

dHL: Digital Health literacy

(d)HL: Health literacy + Digital health literacy

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

ICT: Information and Communication technologies

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GP: General Practitioner

HL: Health literacy

IT: Information Technology

NGO: Non-governmental organization

PMs: Person months

T: Task

WHO: World Health Organization

WP: Work Package

LIST OF ACRONYMS – Partners

CSPA: Consejería de Salud y Servicios Sanitarios – Principado de Asturias

SESPA HUCA: Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias

FICYT: Fundación para el Fomento en Asturias de la Investigación Científica Aplicada y Tecnología

CE: Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation

ISRAA: Institute for Older Care and Sheltered House Services

RMIT: Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology Spain SL

E-SENIORS: Initiation des Seniors aux NTIC Association

EIWH: European Institute of Women's Health

CEI: Central European Initiative – Executive Secretariat

MLHSA: Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration of the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg

UCN: University College of Northern Denmark

MDU: Mälardalen University

SeAMK: Seinäjoki University of Applied Sciences

ADIPER: ADI & SALU SERSOC SL – Socio-sanitary services

ALL DIGITAL: Digital Skills Across Europe

CDC: Caritas Diocesana de Coimbra

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable ‘D2.1 Co-creation methodology’ is intended to set up the theoretical and practical framework for the implementation of the Work Package 2 (WP2) co-creation activities of the IDEAHL project. The aim of this document is to describe common co-creation methods to raise awareness of and discuss about (digital) health literacy across the EU and to engage a variety of stakeholders at local and regional level through dedicated co-creation actions.

Co-creation is a form of collaborative creativity initiated in the private sector that has then been applied to the public environment to help the design and delivery of public services, policies, and products, including for the health care. Co-creation entails a change of perspective on the role of citizens, not only as recipients of care, but also as partners and innovators. In this sense, stakeholders in IDEAHL will be involved in the co-creation and testing of the EU (d)HL Strategy patterned by a methodology to ensure the process is well thought and has specific results.

Co-creation in IDEAHL will occur both offline and online and will be guided by facilitators, who will pose research questions: the answers must be found in the context of the co-design process. Traditional activities will be implemented in all project countries, and they will take different forms depending on the target group. There will be potential focus groups and workshops, but also roleplaying exercises and other activities proposed in the co-creation methodology applied in case by case by the facilitator. In addition to traditional co-creation, WP2 Leader - supported by IDEAHL partners - will conduct further online co-creation exercises and awareness campaigns, especially through social media.

To guide co-creation actions, the first step is to build a comprehensive plan and strategy, as well as to provide a theoretical framework to support partners in all steps of co-creation efforts. To achieve this, the deliverable is composed of 6 Chapters:

Chapter 1 – Introduction. Introduction to the project, WP2, and aims of co-creation.

Chapter 2 – Background, focusing on the theoretical concepts of co-creation and knowledge brokerage, stakeholders, and participatory approaches.

Chapter 3 – ‘Setting the framework’ of WP2, summarising the key results coming from Task (T) 2.2. This task has established the baseline for T2.1 by identifying main challenges, barriers, areas of improvement, and stakeholders of (digital) health literacy in the 4 domains that shall be

considered by the IDEAHL Strategy - health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, and self-care.

Chapter 4 – IDEAHL’s methodology to co-creation, describing the types and timing of planned co-creation activities, as well as partners’ allocated budget for the sessions.

Chapter 5 – Traditional co-creation activities, providing detailed and extensive guidelines and operational steps for the organisation, implementation and monitoring of traditional co-creation activities (T2.3) to be ensured by project partners.

Chapter 6 – Social media campaign and other online actions. Setting up the plan and timeline further co-creation and awareness efforts through social media (T2.4).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 IDEAHL PROJECT

The ‘Improving Digital Empowerment for Active Healthy Living’ project (IDEAHL) aims at developing and testing new models and approaches of intervention and application of (digital) health literacy (hereafter referred as ‘(d)HL’) through the co-creation of a comprehensive and inclusive EU Strategy.

The IDEAHL consortium is composed of 14 multi-disciplinary beneficiary partners and one associated partner from 10 EU Member States, which aim to work hand in hand with patients, citizens, and the broad socio-economic sector at local level. The project has been conducting an extensive mapping of (d)HL research, initiatives, and projects in the EU and beyond. It has reviewed and analysed best practices and ‘champions & survivors’ in these fields to foster knowledge exchange and uptake of selected practices.

Building on these foundations, the next step for IDEAHL is to launch a co-creation process to design and plan its EU (d)HL Strategy, involving over 1,300 different stakeholders, from citizens and patients to healthcare and social services, policy makers, non-health sectors, academia, etc.

The collected feedbacks will allow to develop an inclusive Strategy to improve (d)HL for the benefit of all citizens focusing on health promotion, disease prevention, treatment and (self-)care as well as on monitoring its impact on the wellbeing, productivity, and the economy. The Strategy will pay special attention to social innovation, inclusion, gender, and ethics & privacy dimensions. Finally, a number of actions of the Strategy will be piloted in the 10 project countries. From the testing and evaluation of the pilots, IDEAHL will be able to put forward a common EU monitoring model and indicators for (d)HL levels.

The ultimate purpose of the project is to empower EU citizens in using digital tools to take a more active role in the management of their own health and well-being, as well as supporting social innovations for person-centred care models.

1.2 PURPOSES AND OBJECTIVES

To achieve the above-mentioned objectives, the project will implement co-creation and co-design actions for the EU (d)HL Strategy under the Work Package (WP) 2 – Co-creation of the EU strategy to improve (d)HL.

The **aims of WP2** are to

1) develop a comprehensive and inclusive EU Strategy to improve (d)HL for the benefit of all citizens focusing on health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, and self-care;

2) engage a variety of stakeholders at local and regional level, healthcare professionals, social services professionals, citizens and patients, practitioners from education, etc.

To achieve these objectives, **five tasks are foreseen in WP2:**

- T2.1 Co-creation methodology and roadmap (M7-M9) – Leader: CE
- T2.2 Setting the framework (M5-M9) – Leader: ISRAA
- T2.3 Traditional “co-creation” activities (M10-M16) – Leader: ISRAA
- T2.4 Social media Campaign (M10-M16) – Leader: CE
- T2.5 Development of the EU (d)HL Strategy (M14-M17) – Leader: CSPA

The present deliverable (D2.1) is related to T2.1 and puts forward the design of a co-creation methodology based on the outcomes of WP1 (map health literacy research and practices in Europe and beyond) and T2.2. The deliverable presents a roadmap for the whole IDEAHL co-creation process, particularly, to guide partners with the execution of their traditional co-creation activities (T2.3, T2.4). The co-creation experience will be functional to the final outcome of WP2 - the development of the EU (d)HL Strategy (T2.5).

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR HEALTH

Digital technologies are a driving force for helping citizens and health professionals address preventable risk factors associated with diseases. They can support healthy ageing and facilitate early detection and treatment. Digital solutions are also key to support a shift in care provision by empowering citizens in accessing their personal health data and managing their own health. Although the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the health and care field has become more frequent, challenges to successful deployment of digital technologies applied to health and the improvement of citizens' (d)HL do exist. As stated in the European Union (EU) [eHealth Action Plan 2012-2020](#), the main barriers to the deployment of ICT in healthcare lie in the lack of awareness and confidence in eHealth opportunities among patients, citizens, and healthcare professionals. The [DigitalHealthEurope](#) project has recognised similar barriers: (1) Assumptions that people who have the knowledge to use technology also have knowledge about the health digital tools; (2) Lack of training support; and (3) Difficulties in developing initiatives that reach everyone, especially vulnerable groups.

IDEAHL will seek to **strengthen health systems' resilience and efficiency towards digital transformation**. The project will be an enabler to make citizens and professionals see **the potential of digital tools for active healthy lifestyles and increase people's knowledge on how technology works in health systems**, and which are its benefits. It will enhance a stronger EU and government investment on (d)HL education, along with promoting stakeholder involvement in the development process of (d)HL solutions.

2.2 CO-CREATION CONCEPT

The IDEAHL project plans to co-develop its EU (d)HL Strategy by taking into account feedback and opinions from interested parties and groups of citizens. This feedback will be retrieved through an interactive and multi-step process of co-creation.

Co-creation is a form of collaborative creativity that was initiated by firms first to enable innovation with, rather than simply for their customers (Ramaswamy et al., 2014). Co-creation refers to any act of collective creativity which means that creativity is **shared by two or more people**. These new types of processes encourage new behaviours, roles, and relationships.

Citizens are no longer passive, but they participate as active members of the process providing inputs and they become valuable information source because of their final user perspective.

In the last decades, the concept of co-creation has evolved and been transferred from the business sector to public-private collaboration, as in the case of Living Labs. Living Labs are a relatively new concept of 'Public Private Partnership' in which firms, public authorities and citizens work together to create, validate, and test new services, businesses, markets, and technologies in real-life contexts (Niitamo et al., 2006; Schuurman et al., 2015). The public is considered a co-producer of service, policy/strategy, or innovation and can help the government in solving problems faster and accurately by harnessing a collaborative network of citizen experts (Agranoff, 2007; Ind et al., 2013).

Community participation, being one of the strong features of decentralised planning, is therefore important to achieve socio-economic uplift. Active involvement of the community helps in preparation and execution of effective development action plans by making assessment of the felt needs and simplifying the constraints of the people. Participation of community members in the development planning process also helps mobilise resources for effective plan implementation.

In the last decade, **co-creation** has started to be **applied for the design and delivery of public health services** (Zhang et al., 2015). Current developments in the health and care system display the **changing role of patients from passive recipients of medical services to active partners and co-producers of their health**. The key is to build up the knowledge and confidence of the users to take action themselves in new partnerships with professionals. In this way, there could be more choice, more personalised care, real empowerment of people to improve their health, moving from a service that does things to and for its patients to one which is patient-led, where the service works with patients to support them with their health needs.

The integration of new technologies into the everyday lives of people, businesses and governments also helps to open up public administrations, offering opportunities for collaborative and participatory relationships that allow stakeholders (i.e., citizens, business and non-governmental organisations [NGO]) to collaborate in the design of public services and participate in their delivery to provide more coherent and integrated solutions to complex challenges.

Likewise, **the ambition of IDEAHL is to foster a truly bottom-up approach** by involving all relevant stakeholders to raise awareness of d(HL) and support the definition of areas of improvements and interventions for the project Strategy. In the project each partner will work with different population groups, considering gender and inclusion criteria such as low-income citizens, migrants, women, children, etc. IDEAHL will also pay attention to policy makers whose role in validation/as validators is key for long-term sustainability. It will propose and pilot social innovation initiatives for empowerment of citizens.

2.3 STAKEHOLDER AND PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES

IDEAHL approach lies in the active engagement of **stakeholders**, who can be defined as individuals or groups who affect or are affected by a policy, strategy, or measure. Stakeholders can thus be any type of organisation, including public authorities; research organisations; health and care service providers; formal and non-formal education institutions; business support organisations and business associations; non-profit organisations, including foundations or NGOs; civil society organisations; etcetera.

Stakeholder participation can be conceived as a **process where individuals, groups and organisations are invited and choose to take an active role in making decisions that affect them** (Reed, 2008). Stakeholder participation differs from broader public participation, since stakeholders are only those who can affect or be affected by a decision. **Stakeholder participation** in such contexts has several **benefits** (Cottrell et al., 2015):

- Quality and durability of decisions is enhanced (Fischer, 2000; Beierle, 2002; Reed, 2008). Information from stakeholders brought into the deliberation contributes to avoid unintended consequences of decisions, such as environmental ones, and more adherence of those to existing contexts. More solutions to solving problems could be formulated.
- Social consensus is more easily reached. Stakeholders' engagement increases public understanding of the issues and consequences of different choices and reveals both conflicts and agreements among different stakeholder groups. At the same time, open and inclusive stakeholder engagement, including representatives of different viewpoints, can sometimes resolve differences and build trust in the policy making process and therefore help assure public acceptance of decisions (Kleivink et al., 2012).
- The process of decision-making and final decisions becomes more transparent and legitimate.

Strategy/policy development in health and care needs to include all stakeholders, irrespective of their degree of power and influence (Kujala et al., 2022).

A participatory approach is an approach in which everyone who has a stake in the intervention has a voice, either in person or by representation, and the right to contribute to a decision-making process. In this sense, a participatory approach does not include simple communication where stakeholders receive an information or provide information and knowledge to well-defined questions (Bruce et al., 2010).

Stakeholders need to be engaged early in the process and with an open and interactive approach, allowing them to provide inputs and suggestions for the decisions to be taken and feedback on reformulation of decisions by policy makers. This will be fundamental for the IDEAHL Strategy, and it is why co-creation in the project is functional to the Strategy development process. The table below, describes well the differences among the possible **typologies of participation**, which can be relevant for IDEAHL purposes and activities.

Participation in information giving	The information being shared belongs only to external professionals. People participate by answering questions posed by extractive researchers using questionnaire surveys or such similar approaches. People do not have the opportunity to influence proceedings, as the findings of the research are neither shared nor checked for accuracy.
Participation by consultation	People participate by being consulted, and external agents listen to views. These external agents define both problems and solutions and may modify these in the light of people's responses. Such a consultative process does not concede share in decision-making, and professionals are under no obligation to take on board people's views.
Functional participation	People participate by forming groups to meet predetermined objectives related to the project, which can involve the development or promotion of externally initiated social organisation. Such involvement tends not to be at early stages of project cycles or planning, but rather after major decisions have already been made. These institutions tend to be dependent on external initiators and facilitators but may become self-dependent.
Interactive participation	People participate in joint analysis, which leads to action plans and the formation of new local institutions or the strengthening of existing ones. It tends to involve interdisciplinary methodologies that seek multiple objectives and make use of systematic and structured learning processes. These groups take control/ownership over local decisions, and so people have a stake in maintaining structures or practices.

Table 1. Types of participation. Source: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)

2.4 KNOWLEDGE BROKERAGE

To face the complexity of societal challenges, the **IDEAHL (d)HL Strategy** needs to be **knowledge-based**. ‘**Knowledge brokerage**’ refers to the process of generating knowledge based on user needs, disseminating it, building capacity for its uptake by decision-makers, and finally tracking its application in specific contexts (Meyer, 2010). Knowledge brokerage and its implications are tackled in this section to serve as a basis for a discussion and an agreement on the key characteristics of knowledge brokerage the consortium wants to focus on within the IDEAHL co-creation process.

Knowledge brokerage is not a new concept. In literature, it is generally understood as an intermediary activity that takes place between and within the spheres of science, policy and civil society in order to bridge the research-to-practice gap (Roxborough et al., 2009; Knight et al., 2013), the knowledge-to-action gap (Straus et al., 2009) or, more generally, to manage the boundaries between science, policy and practice (Michaels, 2009) and to link the producers and users of research (Ward et al., 2009).

Such intermediary activities are designed to build relationships and foster effective knowledge exchange. The purpose of knowledge brokerage activities is often related to supporting the identification, access, assessment, interpretation and utilisation of research findings for evidence-based policy making, and the uptake in practice, which addresses an interaction with relevant stakeholder groups or the public in general. Magnuszewski et al. (2010) distinguish between two main groups conceptualising knowledge brokerage slightly differently:

- 1.** The first understands knowledge brokerage as a concept that improves science communication in both directions. In this case, Knowledge Brokerage aims to increase the utilisation of scientific information in decision-making (and practice) by facilitating knowledge exchange through dissemination of research findings, synthesizing existing knowledge and the ‘translation’ of scientific information.
- 2.** The second group doubts that improved communication alone would make a difference. In their point of view knowledge brokerage is about reframing translation and interpretation of knowledge in order to increase the acceptance and use of scientific information by policy makers and practitioners.

Knowledge brokerage activities may be located at different levels – referring to the individual, a group, or an organisation:

a. At the individual level, knowledge brokerage is done by a person, who overtakes the role of a boundary spanner between the different realms of research and policy, strategy and/or practice by translating, transferring, and exchanging knowledge (e.g., consultants, advisors).

b. At the group level of brokering, social capital represents a means through which knowledge is exchanged. The development of social capital within a network or community requires that actors are connected to each other (structural dimension), understand each other's perspectives (cognitive dimension) and trust each other (relational dimension). Through situated interactions, actors engaged in the Knowledge Brokerage activities build up trust and understanding that encourage them to exchange knowledge.

c. At the organisational level of brokering, boundary spanning institutions/organisations may develop: they either could be independent or affiliated to one of the realms (e.g., universities' knowledge transfer departments, liaising departments at ministries, etc.). Knowledge brokers at the organisational level mediate divergent interests by focusing on organisational mechanisms and processes that enable collaboration, and in so doing, they selectively broker knowledge to induce collective action and enhance co-operation amongst actors engaged (Currie et al., 2012).

As described by Currie et al., (2012), much of the literature on knowledge brokerage focuses upon the individual level. However, analysis at the individual level applies to the cases of group and organisational level knowledge brokerage.

Knowledge brokerage includes diverse strategies. These strategies vary in relation to the actors engaged (different types of researchers, policy makers, civil society or other actors), the type of knowledge being shared, and the specific context. Michaels (2009) reviewed knowledge brokerage in the context of policy decision-making and identified six strategies that might be employed in responding to different types of policy problems or policy settings:

- **Inform:** The intent of informing is to disseminate content. In this case, the recipient understands the significance of what is being presented and may well accept the information at face value.
- **Consult:** this process involves someone who is accountable for a problem looking for counselling, seeks someone regarded as having potentially valuable insights, if not solutions, into the problem at hand.

- **Matchmake:** Matchmaking brings together individuals who can contribute to an envisaged action (e.g., policy decision-making). Through brokerage, the actors are brought together; the broker needs to identify what expertise is needed, and who can provide it in order to connect these people.
- **Engage:** engaging as a form of brokering involves the party who is responsible for addressing the problem establishing and implementing a process of involving others with salient expertise.
- **Collaborate:** collaborating involves all participants in jointly framing the process of how they interact with each other, and to negotiate how to scope the problem to be addressed.
- **Build capacity:** Capacity building refers to the ability of people and institutions to do what is required of them. To build capacity in the scope of knowledge brokerage, parties jointly frame a process of interaction and negotiate substance with the intent of addressing multiple dimensions of a problem while considering what can be learned from doing so.

While informing, consulting and matchmaking often require a low level of involvement, engaging, collaborating and capacity building need higher levels of engagement and personal interaction to be effective. IDEAHL will seek to work with the involved stakeholders at the highest level promoting active engagement in the development of the project outputs while promoting awareness and capacity building on health.

The **roles of** individuals/groups/organisations performing **knowledge brokerage** could be quite different, and this shall be taken into account by IDEAHL partners when implementing their co-creation activities.

Gould & Fernandez (1989) developed a knowledge broker typology framework within which a series of brokerage roles could be categorised. These are: co-ordinator, itinerant broker, gatekeeper, representative and liaison.

In the 'co-ordinator' type, all the actors including the broker and the source of knowledge are in the same group. In the 'itinerant broker' type the broker mediates between actors in the same group, but the broker is not part of this group. The 'gatekeeper' screens external knowledge to distribute it within their own group. 'Representative' role is given if a group delegates the brokering role of external knowledge to someone in the group. 'Liaison' is when knowledge is brokered across different groups, neither of which the brokers are members of.

Magnuszewski et al., (2010) reviewed knowledge brokerage activities and categorised the brokers' roles based on this framework. Their results showed that the predominant type was 'representative', followed by the 'gatekeeper'. They also found a clear preference for knowledge roles to belong to the science domain, followed by the preference for the policy domain.

Knowledge brokerage actions need to consider different perspectives and issues concerning the relation between co-creation participants and the way the information and knowledge flow among participants (Turnhout et al., 2013). The list below describes the main issues to be taken into consideration while designing knowledge brokerage actions and the IDEAHL co-creation activities:

- **Relationships of trust and confidence:** The quality of knowledge brokerage depends on the type and quality of relationships between engaged actors; key factors in successful knowledge brokerage and collaboration are relationships of trust and confidence; frequent interaction that reinforces high trust relationships represent a prerequisite for effective knowledge brokering or driving research into practice.
- **Customised activities:** Knowledge brokerage activities which are customised to specific contexts are more likely to support the uptake of evidence into policy decisions and practice.
- **Non-linear process:** One-directional knowledge transfer from the producers to the users of research is not very likely to be beneficial for research utilisation in evidence informed policy and practice (Armstrong et al., 2006).
- **Combining activities:** A combination of different activities, e.g., tailored messages and interactive activities engaging researchers and policy makers to discuss research findings and their potential implications for practice, positively influences the use of research evidence. A process that reaches potential users on multiple levels is considered being very effective in achieving evidence-informed decision-making.
- **Transfer of tailored information:** Decision-makers prefer to receive research evidence in the form of systematic reviews based on the culmination of many studies versus single studies.
- **Tailored activities:** Knowledge brokerage activities should be tailored to suit all actors engaged. Techniques to help facilitate knowledge exchange and transfer among stakeholders should explicitly recognise the diversity of types of knowledge represented by different stakeholders.

- **Communication:** Appropriate communication styles and tools should be chosen according to the different types of stakeholders/actors engaged. The shared language should correspond to different types of knowledge involved.
- **Language barriers:** For activities engaging actors from different language areas, it is important to implement measures (e.g., use of specific tools, provision of translation services, language support, conscious facilitation) to avoid language barriers. This could be particularly relevant for activities engaging actors of different educational backgrounds, but the capability to cope with foreign languages may also differ amongst age groups.
- **Online tools:** Online tools to be used for knowledge brokerage activities need to be carefully chosen and designed in line with the actors' capabilities of using such tools. It needs much effort to mobilise people: for example, in the beginning, certain actors may be quite reluctant in engaging in online interactions; regular training sessions and technical support is a way to facilitate the use of online tools.
- **Relational issues:** It is helpful to address relational issues between those involved in the knowledge brokerage process in order to address differences between communities.
- **Process flexibility:** In order to enhance strategic thinking and adaptive management, openness, iteration and flexibility of the process are important. A certain flexibility of the process is also necessary if adjustments according to participants' needs and expectations are requested.

Finally, for IDEAHL purposes it is important to note that there is some evidence that **personality characteristics of knowledge brokers influence knowledge brokerage activities**. As pointed out before, knowledge brokers may perform a range of roles, which calls for specific skills that may vary according to the different purposes. However, a core set of brokering skills necessary to carry out effective knowledge brokerage is listed here:

- **Personal attributes:** Knowledge brokers should be inquisitive, flexible, inspirational, highly credible, and keenly interested in learning. They should be skilled analysts, able to see the 'big picture' and be able to readily identify links between ideas and pieces of information.
- **Critical appraisal skills:** Knowledge brokers should be able to appraise evidence to evaluate its quality, importance, and applicability to a particular context. They should have knowledge of the sector, the broader environment (e.g., policy context), its key players and controversies - and use this to gauge the applicability and adaptability of new evidence to user contexts.

- **Communication skills:** Knowledge brokers should have strong oral and written communication skills and use a variety of methods targeted to the needs of the diverse stakeholders. They should use active listening skills to gain insight into interests and issues of their network members.
- **Mediation skills:** To function as effective relationship builders, knowledge brokers should be skilled mediators. They assemble teams and foster collaboration amongst individuals and groups who would not normally work together. They reconcile misunderstandings, facilitate the identification of shared goals, and negotiate mutually beneficial roles for all group members.

In IDEAHL, partners will ensure to appoint a co-creation coordinator in charge of co-creation sessions possibly combining these skills and at least having some background in facilitating groups' interactions and management. To conclude, based on the above-described theoretical overview, **IDEAHL knowledge brokerage concept** entails a participatory group process during which participants will **exchange information and ideas for the development of the EU (d)HL Strategy**. This process would last approx. 20 6 months, but at the same time knowledge brokerage activities will be aimed to ensure a long-term engagement of participants.

Knowledge brokerage in IDEAHL will include:

Development, maintenance, and facilitation of networks linking health & care providers, researchers, decision-makers and civil society
Support of social interaction and trust to promote a better understanding of different context
Shaping group learning processes
Synthesising existing knowledge (from different sources)
Support of communication processes
Support for evidence informed decision-making to develop strategies and actions for (d)HL
Guiding citizens & civil society organisations in accessing, appraising, adapting, and applying research evidence
Helping health & care providers, researchers, decision-makers and civil society organisations to define research and policy priorities
Assessing context with attention to supports and barriers for knowledge exchange
Support of capacity building in all the target groups engaged
Helping to translate research needs articulated by non-researchers into research

Table 2 - Knowledge brokerage process

3. SETTING THE FRAMEWORK FOR THE EU STRATEGY (T2.2)

T2.2 deals with the review and formalisation of the **barriers/shortcomings, areas of improvement, stakeholders, and targets/levels of improvement** to be reached by the IDEAHL (d)HL Strategy. The main health domains considered along with the EU Strategy, as requested by the EU, are **health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, and self-care**. The review performed by T2.2 Leader ISRAA was meant: (1) to expand knowledge and key factors of (d)HL to be considered in the project's Strategy development (T2.5); and (2) to outline draft (d)HL initiatives that might be considered for the Strategy roadmap and WP3 pilots. T2.2 analysis was intended to be based on existing data from literature and practice reviews of WP1. As the delivery of WP1 Deliverable 1.1 (Report on (d)HL) was postponed until February 2023 (M10), it was necessary to slightly modify the approach to T2.2.

T2.2 built its analysis mainly from existing experience, knowledge, and desk research performed by the T2.2 Leader. Afterwards, outcomes were cross-checked based on the preliminary available results coming from WP1. The plan is to double check on T2.2 results against the final D1.1 to ensure it is fully in line with the literature and practice reviews performed in WP1.

For the purposes of the present deliverable D2.1, the most crucial and recurrent aspects to consider in relation to shortcomings, areas of improvement, actors to be involved, type of initiatives to be developed and level of implementation for each of the four domains of the Strategy are summarized below. The complete T2.2 analysis document has been shared among the consortium and is available upon request by the European Commission (EC). Finally, it is important to highlight that, among the various outcomes, T2.2 analysis revealed that the four domains of the Strategy present rather common aspects in terms of challenges and improvements.

3.1 HEALTH PROMOTION

Main shortcomings/barriers

Insufficient health literacy not only impacts the lives of individuals because they are unable to properly take care of their health but also constitutes a social and economic challenge. Understanding the reasons for low levels of health literacy helps to identify what barriers to overcome and obstacles to remove. **These are not exclusively attributable to individuals' lack of knowledge/skills, but people's contexts and lifestyles play a significant role.**

Task 2.2 analysis shows that **the information coming from the healthcare system is often perceived by users as too complicated**. At the same time, research methods also do not seem to be enough intuitive. This can lead to overuse, underuse, or incorrect use, which can not only cause unnecessary harm to the people concerned but also create unnecessary costs for the healthcare system.

Obstacles to the success of (d)HL policies also include **cultural barriers**, such as social and economic inequalities and deep-rooted cultural beliefs, which make it difficult to adopt healthier lifestyles, and/or educational attainment. According to the WHO document “From Innovation to Implementation - eHealth in the WHO European Region” (2016), a barrier that cannot be ignored is the **linguistic** one. English is known to be the primary language dominating the web, relevant when we look at disparities in (d)HL. It seems that ethnicity as a single barrier factor may have instead less impact.

Another issue is the sustainability of (d)HL policies, which prove to be effective when they are stable and shared. As a matter of fact, **the lack of a structural and fixed budget dedicated to health literacy policies can significantly limit the activities of (d)HL and their effectiveness**. Add to this, it is underlined **difficulty obtaining high-quality evidence of those interventions**, which reveals a lack of attention in the spheres of evaluation and measurement.

Areas of improvement

When it comes to health promotion, what requires immediate attention is the **shift from a problem-solving-disease perspective to a prevention perspective and the dissemination and correct application of information outside the health context**. Health promotion must be supported especially in the living environment and in everyday life, therefore it is necessary to **focus on everyday life environments** and challenges outside the healthcare system. However, this does not mean that the health system can be side-lined, but that there is a need to improve the information for the users of the system and to make the health system itself more health literate and user-friendly, thus reducing the challenges users face.

Another area of improvement concerns **inequalities in (digital) health literacy**: transferring health promotion efforts from offline to online and mobile devices does not automatically alleviate these inequalities, even with today’s improved access to technology. Health promotion is also essential to enable people with an immigration background to take care of their own health. Therefore, the health information offered should take into account cultural diversity and

language barriers, at the same time health professionals should be aware of this diversity and be able to develop strategies to better address the challenges of limited health literacy. Readability of health-related content found on the internet is still a relevant issue: language and ethnicity should be taken into account, while the use of instant translation services could result in mistakes and misunderstandings. These are important aspects to be addressed for a better adaptation of future (d)HL interventions.

Another aspect to consider is that, although the Internet is becoming increasingly important for seeking health information, **doctors are still the most trusted source of information**. This suggests that **a combination of instruments, including physician live or online consultation**, could be helpful in delivering useful and effective health information using digital information technology. In order to foster the development of health promotion policies and interventions, it is decisive to be able to **demonstrate their impacts on the individual, the community, and the health and social system**. Consequently, one of the areas of focus must be how the benefits can be spread and made known to the community. The measurement and evaluation of the interventions are the keys to strengthening health promotion interventions and also health literacy in a broader sense.

Actors to be involved

Actors can be defined as the people working or living in the sectors, organisations, professions, and societal groups affected by health promotion policies. These are both the beneficiaries or recipients of the interventions and the ones that take part in the implementation of policy activities. Furthermore, it would be auspicious to involve the stakeholders also in the planning phase of these policies, using the co-design methods, because their active participation could ensure more effectiveness. For this to happen, it is essential that **patients, citizens, learners, school students, and health professionals get involved at an early stage**, taking into particular account people in vulnerable groups. As it has already emerged in the course of this document, the centrality of the **involvement of institutional subjects and public bodies and organisations** – especially those working in the fields of education, health, and social services – is crucial. Another group of actors that it is strategic to be engaged is represented by professionals of the media and journalism, who have a crucial role in the communication and dissemination of information.

Type of initiatives to be developed

What needs to be emphasised first and foremost is the importance of **networking for the development and implementation of policies and interventions**, reaching out to involve policymakers and institutional actors at the local, national and European levels. There are already networks to support and foster, such as the WHO European Action Network on Health Literacy for Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases (2019). Collaboration and support within these networks are as crucial as any collaboration working to systematically develop, implement or evaluate health literacy.

In most cases, health literacy, and thus health promotion interventions, have mainly been addressed within specific healthcare settings or diagnostic groups. However, more integrated and wide-ranging approaches have the potential to better identify needs and improve the response across the lifespan by reducing barriers and improving support systems. It is essential to support the **development and implementation of both further national and transnational projects that expand and broaden the variety of contexts, reaching different populations and different stages of life** at the same time, and of health literacy interventions in specific areas of the population that are or are at risk of being marginalized.

Another recurring element, which should continue to be implemented and indeed strengthened, is the **use of co-creation in the development and implementation of interventions**. The use of methods that attempt to actively involve all stakeholders, such as users, employees, collaborators can support the creation of context-sensitive initiatives that improve local empowerment and sustainability.

Summarising the main findings and suggestions that could help health promotion, the following points have been identified:

- Everyday life environment
 - Enable the education system to promote (d)HL early in life.
 - Promote (d)HL in professional life and at the workplace.
 - Strengthen (d)HL in dealing with consumption and nutrition offers.
 - Facilitate the handling of health information in the media.
 - Empower communities to strengthen the (d)HL of citizens in their living environment.

- Healthcare system
 - Integrate (d)HL as a standard at all healthcare system levels.
 - Facilitate navigation within the healthcare system, increase transparency, and reduce administrative barriers.
 - Create comprehensible, effective communication between health and care professionals and users.
 - Facilitate and strengthen patient participation.

- Life with chronic diseases or conditions
 - Integrate (d)HL into caring for the chronically ill.
 - Facilitate and support a health-literate handling of disease/condition progression and its consequences.
 - Strengthen the self-management ability of people with chronic diseases or conditions and their families;
 - Promote (d)HL for coping with everyday life and chronic disease.

- Research
 - Develop (d)HL research.
 - Involve citizens in (d)HL research.

Level of implementation

One of the main relevant studies on the determinant elements for the adoption of “Health promotion” initiatives and their success has been developed in the perimeter of the **DEMATEL-Decision-Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory in 2021**. This study has deployed a **method of analysis of the main factors that play a role in health promotion implementation**. The proposed DEMATEL method constructs a cause-effect model of health promotion, and places forward suggestions and strategies for improvement based on the evaluation of the results. This research compared the original DEMATEL model with a Modified DEMATEL (M-DEMATEL) to identify the success factors of health promotion. The main purpose of this research is to derive the combined effect of both methods. Connections and differences between the two methods were presented, showing which dimensions should be considered as powerful levers for any kind of health promotion initiative.

According to the results of both methods, “**leadership**”, “**communication channel**” and “**budget**” are the most important and influential factors when promoting healthy diets.

“**Leadership**” is the ability to make subordinates obey voluntarily, with voluntary being the key word. As an example, concerning the non-profit organization, the charisma, kindness, and compassion of the leader can drive the behaviour of the volunteers and members. Therefore, leadership is authoritative when followers are willing to obey because they believe the leader’s directions represent followers’ self-interest and also the mission of the organization. Leadership was identified as the factor most frequently associated with health promotion.

In the case of the “**Communication channel**”, health promotion may benefit from the use of mass media to promote positive health behaviours. Thus, health promotion campaigns that combine mass media and communication channels with the distribution of free or reduced-price health-related products are effective in improving healthy behaviours.

It is believed that “**Budget**” is one of the important factors in carrying out an activity or campaign for any organization. Budget requirements depend on program focus, resources available, and incentives incorporated into the program and the specific health promotion activity. The majority of non-profit organizations depend largely on donations from the public. Budget is important and crucial for non-profit organizations because it can be a way to achieve organizational sustainability and provide resources for campaigns and activities.

3.2 DISEASE PREVENTION

Main shortcomings/barriers

Initiatives to support (d)HL on disease prevention seem to be relatively widespread across Europe. However, in most cases, they appear to be **circumstantial and of a time-limited nature**. This observation, although not extendable to all of them, makes it possible to state that, generally speaking, the **poor systematization and homogenization** of these practices could represent a barrier. Such situation entails the risk that the number of citizens benefiting will remain relatively small and a possible discontinuity in the provision of educational opportunities. Ensuring continuity and homogeneity would be in fact conducive to more awareness raising, better knowledge, and solid education. A further important element **concerns citizens’ capacity to reach and understand information about health, including disease prevention**. Indeed, inequalities can be detected between people with a higher educational background and those

who quit the educational pathway around the age of 15 (Eurobarometer, 2014). Inequalities between those with a higher level of schooling and those with a lower one seems to increase even more in the case of (d)HL. Here, additional difficulties are also related to the capacity to discern which online sources are truly reliable among the large quantity present. According to the survey on digital health literacy developed in April 2011 by The Health on the net Foundation, searching for disease prevention and health-related information on the web finds additional critical issues in the low specificity of search results, their general disorganisation, and the excessive amount of information. This last observation suggests that citizens with little or no literacy in the English language (that is predominant on the Web) and/or migrants and refugees, often unfamiliar with the one spoken in the migration country, are more exposed to the risk to face barriers confronted with the rest of the population. Of course, this is extendable also to health literacy that does not pass through the web. Finally, accessibility of information turns out to be a diriment variable, especially with regards to the online one. Those who do not possess good digital literacy are in fact penalized. **Absence or weak digital alphabetization** is intended both as a lack of ability to properly use tools and as the absence of familiarity with the internet and its features, with the consequent difficulty or incapacity of orienting, discerning, and understanding. Finally, **accessibility** is strictly connected to possessing the **technological infrastructure** that allows access, such as PCs, smartphones, tablets, and first and foremost, the Internet network connection.

Areas of improvement

Based on the above, the following can be considered areas of improvement:

- **accessibility of information**, in its various declinations;
- **attention to the specificities of certain segments of the population** (older adults, migrants, low-literate, other vulnerable people).

Developing programmes that take these variables into account could allow more citizens to be approached, ensuring more widespread awareness and knowledge. Systematization of programs aimed at fostering (d)HL and disease prevention can be a key element to ensure this result. Equally relevant seems their diversification according to the target audience. Such improvement could open doors to greater and more effective dissemination, increased quality, and, hopefully, a more significant impact on the population. Communication should also be developed by the

target audience, identifying the appropriate channels, the register to be adopted, and the proper way to organize the information. This would facilitate accessibility.

Actors to be involved

As for health prevention domain, a primary role should be played by **public institutions** which should ensure the systematization and homogenization of initiatives targeting disease prevention (and (d)HL in general), whose patchy and often extemporaneous nature, as stated above, can be a limitation in terms of incisiveness and effectiveness. In addition, it would be essential to encourage the active participation of individuals and community – including the so-called “hard to reach” and people belonging to the vast range of the “minorities” – in the design and definition of these policies at the local, regional and national level before their enactment. This would not only ensure greater accessibility, but also greater sensitivity, awareness, and responsibility on the part of the citizen, who would no longer be just a user, but would have an active and proactive role. Such circumstances could ensure their stronger effectiveness. Indeed, disease prevention represents a theme that would significantly benefit from the creation of a dialogue between the healthcare institution and the citizen, who is in fact required to enact virtuous behaviours in order to implement it.

Type of initiatives to be developed

The policies developed would first benefit from good coordination between the local, regional, and national dimensions and their actors, so as to be as coherent as possible and potentially equally widespread throughout the territory. Similarly important would be their capacity to reach individuals regardless of their differences and specificities. They should therefore foresee training occasions, courses, and initiatives diversified according to the subject’s specifics. Ad hoc structured consulting materials and communication strategies would also be useful to this scope, adopting differentiated registers and communication channels. Attention to the territory constitutes another important variable: the territorial characteristics (type of population, infrastructures present, organization of services...) should be accounted to adapt them, making them really accessible. In short, initiatives and policies should leverage common objectives at a macro level, as well as an equally homogeneous territorial diffusion, but paying attention to differentiate both according to the target and to local specificities. To this scope, the creation of alliances with the various agencies of the territory, even of an informal nature, such as

associations of citizens, cultural and recreational centres, schools, and other relevant stakeholders, represents another important keystone.

Level of implementation

Policies oriented towards (d)HL on disease prevention seem to have reached a fair degree of implementation in different European countries. Implementation must be here understood in the sense of **dissemination** rather than actual advancement and systemization. In fact, it is difficult to state how deep-rooted these policies actually are and how far they represent structured and lasting initiatives. Whether they are policies issued at the state or regional level, guidelines, European commission-funded projects, or local initiatives, it **is hard to find accurate information on their actual concretization and their sustainability**, partly preventing such evaluation. In this respect, it should be also underlined that no detailed data is generally available with regard to their impact, often lacking an impact assessment, an element that would allow a more accurate evaluation of their level of implementation. Many of the initiatives, particularly those of a very local character, and those linked to projects financed by the European Commission or other fundings, also seem to be of an **extemporary nature**. It is, therefore, possible to state that the spread of (d)HL, including but not limited to disease prevention, appears to be good, but it is not possible to verify its degree of real development, structuring, and territorial impact.

3.3 TREATMENT

Main shortcomings/barriers

When interventions fail to address the specific needs of groups and communities in treatment and care, average improvements in population health can conceal widening health **inequalities**. Therefore, it should always be questioned whether new interventions reach those who are often not considered to prevent the unintentional widening of the health gap. By genuinely and effectively involving all stakeholders, including vulnerable groups, interventions are likely to be more appropriate for a wider number of people and support WHO's mission to leave no one behind.

Areas of improvement

When considering approved actions in most of the national plans to comprehensively increase access to good treatments, one area of improvement appears the necessity of a change in patient

role, preferably by adopting the shared decision-making model. Such a model is based on the collaboration between patients and members of the healthcare professionals' team, and it is characterized by a process of an equal and shared decision on the care pathway. Studies show that shared decision-making can lead to an increase in knowledge, active participation in the treatment process, and an improvement in the communication between physicians and patients, that is why it is fundamental to involve the healthcare system, with its organizations and actors, in the improvement of health literacy and work towards the development of a system that is user-friendly and health literate at all levels. Its aim should be for all users to express their needs, make informed decisions and participate actively in treatment and care because communication problems can have negative effects on the course of treatment. In addition, the German National Action Plan-Health Literacy Promoting health literacy (2021), stated that chronic diseases currently constitute the most diffuse type of disease, creating considerable challenges with regard to health literacy and self-management. At the same time, chronic illnesses require particular skills in terms of dealing with health-relevant information, for example when navigating the healthcare system or making decisions about treatment and care options. In this sense, communication seems a relevant area of improvement to be considered. More specifically it would be important to create comprehensible, effective communication between health professionals and users and improve communication and information in order to make informed decisions also in the advanced stages of illness and at the end of life, to avoid or reduce treatment-related stress and unnecessary suffering, and to maintain a good quality of life. According to IC-HEALTH - Deliverable 1–1 - Report on key factors, drivers, barriers, and trends on digital health literacy, it would be important to strengthen ICT for health and well-being (eHealth) as it is becoming a key area with high growth potential and possibilities for innovation in Europe, and which can enhance the quality of care. eHealth has the potential to empower citizens to improve their management of health and disease, improve prevention, enable more accurate diagnosis and treatment and facilitate communication between healthcare professionals and patients. It can also contribute to more equal access to healthcare while facilitating access to health information.

Actors to be involved

The main actors are undoubtedly the health and social care sectors, organizations and professions, as well as citizen interventions, both those who participate in the implementation of policy activities. These actors, together with relevant territorial stakeholders, should be

involved in the design and local adaptation of policies through participatory strategies. This is with a view to laying the groundwork for their greater effectiveness. Important at this stage is the involvement of people from vulnerable groups, such as seniors, migrants, socioeconomically excluded groups, children in socioeconomically disadvantaged families, and prisoners. Equally important is the active presence of institutional actors and public agencies and organizations, primarily those working in the fields of education, health and social services.

Type of initiatives to be developed

Making people with low health literacy aware of their rights and involving patients in treatment and care is particularly challenging. That is why it is necessary to develop standards in care facilities on how patients' voice can be taken into consideration during each phase of treatment and care ("no decision about me without me"), and at the same time increase support in recognizing patients' rights with respect to service provision.

Level of implementation

There are examples of national HL programs (such as The United Kingdom's "NHS Long Term Plan" 2019, Scotland's health literacy action plans 2014 "Making It Easy" and 2017 "Making It Easier", Germany's 2018 "National Action Plan – Health Literacy" or Portugal's 2019 "Health Literacy Action Plan") or other forms of national health strategies that do comprise aspects of (d)HL and attention on how to get access to the best treatment to assist the increasing number of people needing care and the intensity of support they require by (1) growing visibility and concern about areas of longstanding unmet health need (for example in young people's mental health services); (2) expanding frontiers of medical science and innovation, introducing new treatment possibilities that a modern health service should rightly be providing (for example, new cell and gene therapies). Also, technology is an important resource to be considered as it is written in the IC-HEALTH project (see Deliverable 1.1-Report on key factors, drivers, barriers, and trends on digital health literacy), using Big Data in health has many potential benefits. It may contribute to, for example, increasing the effectiveness and quality of treatments available for patients, widening possibilities for disease prevention by identifying risk factors at the population, sub-population, and individual levels, improving pharma co-vigilance and patient safety and reducing inefficiency and waste.

3.4 SELF-CARE

Main shortcomings/barriers

It is often hard to estimate what the costs of launching, implementing, and maintaining (d)HL strategies and actions are, although there is wide consensus in acknowledging that a higher degree of self-care will result in smaller financial strain on the national health systems. Simultaneously, it will also represent a lighter burden on the economic allowance of people by preventing them from experiencing serious health conditions that might be costly to sustain. With the exception of singular, specific projects and trials that depend on a fixed budget, it is usually not clear how much the implementation of a policy would cost, especially within a broader evaluation model of its efficacy.

Indeed, what seems to be the biggest shortcoming in the vast majority of European policies, action plans and initiatives is the lack of an appropriate evaluation and monitoring model that could demonstrate whether the foreseen (or deployed) actions will actually generate a positive outcome. Similarly, when such policies do include an evaluation plan, as in Portugal's 2019 Health Literacy Action Plan, it is difficult to identify results and whether an overview and analysis of findings, feedback, and output has taken place (or whether it is being carried out right now). Despite the lack of data in this sense, it seems that, according to WHO's recommendations, there is a need to place a stronger focus on the evaluation of results within a theoretical work that will subsequently instruct further actions, if required. With regards to self-care outcomes (and other sub-topics of HL alike), there appears to be a certain degree of detachment from the eventual national guidelines and the various concrete projects, actions, and initiatives that are carried out at the local level. On the one hand, it is not clear how much of a political commitment is invested in the topic of Health Literacy as an important component of a comprehensive health policy and strategy, particularly in the direction of an increased level of self-care and management by the public. On the other hand, the distance between several actors (policy makers; health professionals; citizens) in the deployment of HL strategies and actions for the enhancement of self-care, and their univocal direction of relationship, without real exchange of views, does not produce an informed and dialogic discourse that could eliminate the risk of complicating the engagement of the public and its uptake of the proposed solutions.

Lastly, as health literacy levels struggle across Europe, many policies and initiatives still dedicate too little attention to the potential role that digital/mobile technologies and social media could

play in promoting self-care. This rings particularly through with respect to people in later life that is traditionally the beneficiary group that most drags behind in the use of digital technologies. While there is quite a strong focus on the health literacy of children and, simultaneously, while there is a number of policies to stimulate the training in the use of digital technologies, these two often do not seem coordinated within a general comprehensive HL strategy that looks with as much care to older individuals.

Areas of improvement

A lot of attention is recently being put on increasing the simplicity of texts and processes (see, for example, the New Zealand Plain Language Bill that was approved in October 2022). To simplify language means actually improving the accessibility of contents to the wider public and when it comes to matters of health this implies eliminating exclusive medical jargon and limiting sources of difficulty related to numeracy and literacy. It is important that guidelines, information materials, and initiatives that wish to stimulate self-care are fully understandable for the majority of beneficiaries. Other aspects that should be taken into account when designing (d)HL policies directed at promoting self-care consist of planning ahead for a thorough scheme of evaluation that considers the actions that are being put into place or that could be implemented according to the set guidelines. To conduct project initiatives along a certain methodology does not bring effective results if these are not monitored and weighted within a structured view of what the impact is achieved (compared to what was desired), how much it costs to achieve that impact, and what should be done next according to this result. The scrutiny of results is therefore a necessary step that should inform the subsequent decisions on how to proceed with the path that has been undertaken, or on how to tweak the proposed solutions if they have been unsuccessful.

It is desirable that citizens be more widely involved in shaping policies and initiatives together with policy- and decision-makers, as well as with health professionals. Too often the HL strategies are based on a training approach that sees a one-directional relationship between the trainer (health professional or other) and the citizens, who are seen as mere recipients of content designed from a "top-down" perspective. Considering they are not only to be considered the objects of self-care initiatives, but the actual subjects who will have to take the issue into their hands, it seems only appropriate that they are truly empowered at all stages of the process.

Another area of improvement would be to invest more generously in a more comprehensive mobile and social media strategy. With the increasing level of digital literacy and the widespread use of mobile devices and social media, with which most people are already familiar, it would make sense to plan a robust action plan that seeks to exploit the pervasiveness of these technologies. Although there is already a lot of investment in the training for digital literacy and the improvement of digital skills, this is not usually organically coordinated with HL strategy, while the individual interface of mobile technologies and social media would be the most suitable instrument to promote personalized self-care.

Actors to be involved

The wide variety of policies and initiatives that are currently being deployed around Europe insist on the engagement of several different levels of stakeholders where the one constant is the involvement of citizens as end-users and beneficiaries, particularly considering they are the main actors that need to actively take things into their hands in order to put self-care habits into practice. Nevertheless, individuals and communities should be brought into the process at an earlier stage and with a rather more active role that could establish a dialogue with regional and national institutions as well as with health professionals and trainers alike. Indeed, the community dimension, as opposed to the general "nation-wide" policies and to the individual repercussion of these policies, could be the right scope on which to invest by collectivizing responsibility within the limits of a recognizable and relatable group of people that are close to each other, either geographically or for social and cultural reasons. As is the case for the project initiatives developed by the City of Stoke-on-Trent, or by the OEPGK (Österreichische Plattform Gesundheits Kompetenz – the Austrian Health Literacy Alliance), many programs have been developed explicitly around one specific community, rooting the mission of the project in the local identity and for the local wellbeing by tailoring the activities around the people belonging to the same local group.

In order to best capitalize on the engagement of citizens and communities it is important to win the support of and work collaboratively with national, regional, and local partners who can, on the one hand, provide financial and technical assistance, and on the other hand, help reiterate and multiply the effort of engagement directed towards the public. This is particularly true when such partners enjoy a sense of reliability and trust from the public's perspective. For this reason, it is recommendable that even policies at the national level foresee direct involvement and a strong collaboration with local partners and especially with those who can be trusted and

represent "familiar faces" for the local communities such as not-for-profit organizations, foundations, local cultural associations, schools, GPs, etc.

Type of initiatives to be developed

It is recommendable that general large-scope policies be implemented via a number of projects and initiatives that are coordinated within a wider, comprehensive vision that has set clear objectives and results. The projects that can be observed at the European level, even if implemented locally, often seem to be directed autonomously outside of a coordinated effort that seeks to achieve an impact within the established logical framework. As aforementioned, it is desirable that such projects and initiatives being developed at the closest possible level to citizens and communities, considering the need to stimulate the uptake of self-care habits. For this reason, the initiatives should try to involve local partners and stakeholders in the financial and technical investment, by inspiring them to adopt the mission of the wider (d)HL policies. Similarly, these partners and stakeholders should be involved, alongside the citizens themselves, in the initial stages of the process, from its design to the setting of the objectives to be pursued and the methodology to be deployed.

Level of implementation

The current level of implementation of most national frameworks and policies appears to be at a quite early stage. As the sample of policies considered in this study comprises quite recent in time instances, it may be that these are still being implemented or need to find a concrete application through projects and initiatives, and therefore data coming from results and feedback still needs to be gathered or harmonized in structured reports. Nevertheless, as illustrated earlier on, most often there seems to be no clear strategy for the evaluation and monitoring of results and therefore there is uncertainty regarding whether, when, and how such data will be available and who will analyse them. In fact, there are various examples of projects and other kind of initiatives that have been deployed in recent years, but they seem to be rather extemporaneous. Lastly, in recent years the general global attention regarding health might have slightly shifted due to the emergence of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic that is dragging on well into 2022. This urgent issue appears to have paralyzed the production of new legislative and strategic documents on (d)HL, although it could be said that all health recommendations spread by national and regional governments during the pandemics represent nothing but instances of self-care itself, with respect to the COVID-19 disease.

4. IDEAHL'S METHODOLOGY TO CO-CREATION

Co-creation in IDEAHL will happen **offline and online** and will be **guided by facilitators**, who will pose established research questions (see Chapter 5): the answers shall be found in the context of the co-design process. Co-creation activities will take different forms and are described in T2.3 and T2.4 of the Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement.

4.1 TYPES OF CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

The following activities are expected to be executed under WP2:

ALL PARTNERS: Traditional activities (face-to-face, virtual, or hybrid depending on their preferences, target groups, and, if applicable, COVID-19 evolution) will be implemented in all project countries. These will take different forms according to the target group: focus groups, workshops, role-playing/games exercises proposed in the co-creation methodology applied by the facilitator. These events may be complemented by offline work, surveys, direct contact with each participant, etc. Finally, co-creation will be also tailored to policy makers, along with a panel of (d)HL experts to provide feedback for the Strategy.

CE (with support of partners): Social media campaign informs the general public and targeted organisations on the development of the (d)HL EU Strategy and enable collecting feedback. Different actions are planned in digital mode:

- **Calendar of posts** prepared by CE and shared on IDEAHL's social media. All partners will be asked to re-share them (and translate if needed) through their own channels. In addition, it is foreseen to try to engage national/local or European influencers to support in the IDEAHL awareness raising campaign about (d)HL and project purposes and impacts.
- Additional online co-creation exercises, led by ISRAA and CE, for IDEAHL partners and dedicated experts to help define the structure and content of T2.5 (Development of the EU (d)HL Strategy) and D2.3 (Report on co-creation).

Figure 1 - WP2 phases and interconnections

4.2 PARTNERS' ALLOCATED BUDGET

Partners have dedicated **personnel efforts** in the form of Person Months (PMs) allocated to WP2 activities, which can be distributed across WP2 tasks by each partner upon their convenience and internal organisation.

Partner	Allocated PMs on WP2	Partner	Allocated PMs on WP2
CSPA	-	EIWH	6.00
SESPA HUCA	0.50	CEI	5.00
FICYT	7.40	MLHSA	4.00
CE	9.00	UCN	3.00
ISRAA	8.00	MDU	3.00
RMIT	8.00	SeAMK	6.00
RMIT-EU	4.00	ADIPER	8.00
RMIT-UNI	4.00*	ALL DIGITAL	6.00
E-SENIORS	6.00	CDC	8.00

*Provided with own resources. Not EC Contribution

Table 3 - Person months (PMs) efforts allocated to partners for WP2 activities.

In addition, relevant partners can use budget under **Purchase costs for the practical organisation of the co-creation workshops/events**, e.g., renting a venue, printing dissemination material, purchasing resources to conduct activities, catering costs for small coffee breaks, etc.

4.3 CALENDAR OF ACTIVITIES

- WP2 Start month: M5 (Sept. 2022)
- WP2 End month: M17 (Sept. 2023)

	Year 1												Year 2											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
WP2 Co-creation of the EU strategy to improve (d)HL																								
Task 2.1 Co-creation methodology and roadmap																								
Task 2.2 Setting the framework																								
Task 2.3 Traditional "co-creation" activities																								
Task 2.4 Social media campaign																								
Task 2.5 Development of the EU (d)HL Strategy																								

Figure 2 - WP Calendar

5. TRADITIONAL CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES (T2.3)

Chapter 5 provides an overview of expected work and deadlines for the organisation and set-up of T2.3 activities. The methodology and roadmap set in this Chapter will help to facilitate a smooth preparation and implementation of co-creation, avoiding potential delays or bottlenecks. It is crucial to respect the given timeline for co-creation as much as possible since the development of the Strategy and the sub-sequent WP3 pilot phase depends on this task/phase/these activities.

5.1 T2.3 REQUIREMENTS FOR THE CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

Each organisation that is part of the IDEAHL consortium is expected to **deliver at least 2 co-creation sessions for each of its selected population target group(s)**. If project partners envisage to organise more sessions, it is advisable not to surpass/exceed a maximum of 5 co-creation events per group, not to demand too much effort from involved participants and not to risk losing their motivation. Section 5.7 describes how to implement the co-creation sessions.

Beyond the organisation of specific sessions, which represents a contractual commitment for partners towards the EU, upon their needs, partners shall be free to promote complementary approaches and methods to collect further knowledge on (d)HL in the citizen's everyday life. For example, by inviting co-creation participants to 'work' offline via dedicated documents or surveys, or to use other cultural probes designed for the purpose. These activities can add an extra value and complement knowledge retrieved from traditional co-creation. However, it must be clarified that this complementary effort does not substitute the 2 co-creation sessions. Further guidance is provided in Section 5.7.

Finally, it must be highlighted that one IDEAHL partner (CDC) had planned to conduct individual interviews with caregivers (both formal and informal) and other social agents, instead of organising group co-creation sessions, as per the Grant Agreement. Exceptionally for this partner, and only for these target groups, interviews will be accepted as a substitute for co-creation sessions. However, it is recommended that CDC holds one joint meeting (onsite/online) to present the project, make the participants known, and explain the research questions to be addressed during the individual interviews. For the primary groups of older adults and low-income citizens, CDC will, like all other partners, conduct joint focus group sessions.

5.2 CO-CREATION PHASES

Three phases are part of/involved in/included in the IDEAHL T2.3 co-creation process:

Figure 3 - Phases and steps for traditional co-creation activities under Task 2.3

5.3 PARTNERS' ROLES, RESPONSIBILITIES AND PLANNING

Type and number of stakeholders are included in the Grant Agreement (GA) and reported in Table 2 (see below). It also provides a preliminary calendar of activities and preferred modalities/locations for each partner. As stated in the Grant Agreement, at least 1300 citizens and professionals will be recruited for the co-creation activities. However, some partners foresee to increase the recruitment numbers, which will be considered as additional effort.

Partner (country)	Target group(s)	No	Expected No and type of co-creation	Co-creation location / modality	Examples of needs & topics to address for EU Strategy as per GA
CSPA / SESPA (ES)	Migrants	100	5 face-to-face meetings plus virtual meetings upon needs	These activities will take place in the facilities provided by the municipality: prisons, hospitals, schools... (Principality of Asturias)	Elements favoring their integration in the country; how to maintain good mental health; use of language in eHealth products/services for easy understanding.
	Low-income citizens	100	5 face-to-face meetings plus virtual meetings upon needs		How to adjust (d)HL Strategy with free resources available in the community (ex: telecentres and other social resources).
	Prisoners	100	5 face-to-face meetings		Digital tools to increase and maintain better levels of self-care and promote better life habits. Previous experiences have shown high acceptance from this group.
	30 school children (6 to 12 years old)	30	2 face-to-face meetings		Barriers are they facing; interests in getting information about health and in which format; would they like to ask for help to improve their (d)HL; requirements and needs related to devices interfaces adaptation.
	Pregnant women	5	2 face-to-face meetings		(d)HL in clinical practice; perceived patients' approach to eHealth and (d)HL; use of digital tools; gender impact in healthy lifestyles.
	Caregivers	100	5 face-to-face meetings plus virtual meetings upon needs		Prevent caregiver overload, search for own time and care for emotional well-being; creating support networks among professionals; interoperability between health and social care.
	Health professionals and social workers	100			
CE (ES)	Young women	20	1 online kick off meeting online and 2 face-to-face meetings (complemented by offline work/feedback when relevant)	Online/CE office (Las Palmas de Gran Canaria)	Needs, expectations, interests related to digital support/services for cancer prevention, mental health, healthy lifestyles.
	Regional/national EU policy makers	10	1 face-to-face meeting in Brussels with EU/national policy makers and 1 additional online as follow-up (complemented by offline feedback when relevant)	Online/Brussels	Feedback on the Strategy's scope and aims as well as the different drafts of the Strategy.

ISRAA (IT)	Autonomous older people	50	3 rounds of face-to-face meetings, 1 round video WhatsApp.	The activities will be hosted at ISRAA's facilities; Senior's' clubs (if convenient and/or possible).	Software adaptation for health support; info about health they would like to receive digitally; what barriers they are facing; devices interfaces adaptation; who they would like to ask help to improve health literacy.
	Older people in fragile conditions	30	3 rounds of face-to-face meetings, 1 round video WhatsApp.		How to improve (d)HL in informal and formal clinical practice; how to support families and relatives; privacy and ethics; role of social services in (d)HL.
	Caregivers, social agents	50	3 face-to-face meeting, 1 online co-creation exercise engaging the IDEAHL consortium and Advisory Board as well as requesting specific written input from stakeholders in an online collaborative space upon needs.		
RMIT (ES)	Digital literacy and digital health experts	20	2 online meetings	Online	Advice about the information collected and analyzed in WP1 and feedback on the map developed from this information.
E-SENIORS (FR)	Autonomous older people living in their private homes	10	3 rounds meetings, possibly of face- to-face.	ESE office (Paris)	Usability of digital tools; needs related to the use of digital tools for health; (d)HL perceptions, barriers, and opportunities
	Older people with minor impairments linked to ageing	5	3 rounds meetings, possibly of face- to-face.		Requirements on health-related information they need to receive, which they perceive as useful to stay healthy and active.
	Informal caregivers	10	3 rounds meetings, possibly of face- to-face.		What is perceived useful to support relatives or people they assist in terms of (d)HL.
EIWH (IE)	Young women	20	2 in person focus groups.	EIWH facilities (Dublin and Galway) or online.	E-tools for immunization, prevention of cervical and breast cancer, healthy lifestyles; digital access to screening programs.
	Women from the Women's Health	5	2 in person focus groups.		Reasons for low advance in eHealth.

	Task Force				
	Nurses, health practitioners, pharmacists.	20	2 in person focus groups.		(d)HL in clinical practice; perceived patients' approach to eHealth and (d)HL; use of digital tools for remote disease management; gender impact in healthy lifestyles.
CEI (IT)	National and regional EU policy makers	20	2 face-to-face/online meetings.	Online/CEI Headquarters	Feedback on different drafts of the Strategy; (d)HL and COVID-19 (WHO task force).
MDH (SE)	People with disabilities	10	5-10 face to face sessions and additional online meetings upon needs.	MDH premises (Sweden)	Access to (d)HL solutions and digital tools for health services; needs related to (d)HL.
	People with immigrant background	20			Access to (d)HL solutions and digital tools for health services; needs related to digital literacy and (d)HL; change to technology; social/cultural barriers.
	Policy makers	10			Policies to enhance (d)HL, face barriers, and increase opportunities.
UCN (DK)	Children diagnosed with diabetes	20	One cultural probe examination + 2 face-to-face workshops.	Online/UCN premises	How adapt software for health support; what barriers are they facing; interests in getting information about health and in which format; would they like to ask for help to improve their (d)HL; requirements and needs related to devices interfaces adaptation.
	Formal and informal caregivers	60	2 face-to-face workshops and 1 survey		How to improve (d)HL; ethics & privacy; key features for (d)HL training and tools; what digital literacy elements can be improved with their work.
MLHSA (DE)	People with a low social index (e.g., unemployed)	30	3-4 rounds of online meetings (face-to-face depending on COVID-19 evolution)	Online (or at the Ministry of Social Affairs Hamburg premises)	Age friendly environments; patient empowerment; low-threshold access; increase life quality; training/support on digital tools.
	Migrants	20	3-4 rounds of online meetings (face-to-face depending on COVID-19 evolution)		Health equal opportunity and patient empowerment; training/support on digital tools; increase life quality.
SeAMK (FI)	Healthcare, social work and elderly care students	40	4 online meetings and 1 face-to-face meeting	Online/SeAMK campus	Ways to promote (d)HL; how to apply (d)HL in the future contact with patients and clients.

	Healthcare, social work and elderly care lecturers	6	1 online meeting and 1 face-to-face meeting		How to teach students principles of (d)HL to tackle the issue in their future career.
	Healthcare, social work and elderly care professionals	6	2 online meetings		(d)HL in clinical practice; perceived patients' requirements in this topic.
ADIPER (ES)	Seniors, families, caregivers and social agents	200	2 face-to-face workshops and at least 2 online workshops	Online/ Sevilla, Badajoz, Madrid.	(d)HL in clinical and professional practice: perceived patients' and clients' requirements in the topic.
All Digital (BE) <i>Additional:</i>	Adults with low access to digital tools	25	2 face-to-face workshops	Online/Brussels	User-friendly requirements for development of digital tools for health; how to increase access to health-related ICT tools among citizens.
	Women	10	2 face-to-face workshops		Needs and interests about ICT for their own health and family health' management.
	<i>All Digital members</i>	80	<i>4 face-to-face meetings</i>		<i>These are additional activities proposed by the partner.</i>
	<i>All Digital Stakeholders</i>	100	<i>2 face-to-face workshops with stakeholders during the General Assembly and ALL DIGITAL Week.</i>		<i>These are additional activities proposed by the partner.</i>
CDC (PT)	Seniors in fragile conditions	30	Min 2 focus groups	Online/CDC facilities i.e., Centro Comunitário de Inserção; Centro São José (Coimbra)	Experiences related to (d)HL; technologies interesting for health information.
	Low – income citizens	10	Min 2 focus groups		How to achieve HL needs of this group using technologies.
	Formal & informal caregivers, social agents	20	Exceptionally for this partner, and these target groups only, interviews will be accepted as a substitution for co-creation sessions.		(d)HL difficulties and opportunities in clinical practice; role of informal caregivers in (d)HL of older adults, their needs and challenges.

Table – 3 - Partners' roles, responsibilities, and planning for T2.3 co-creation activities.

With respect to the healthcare related target groups mentioned in the above table, for the sake of clarify, it is worth distinguishing the difference between certain typologies of stakeholders expected to be recruited by partners:

- **Formal caregivers:** With formal caregivers, one should consider people that are paid for their health & care related services and have had training and education in providing care. These could be e.g., doctors, nurses, and other trained professionals that work in the fields of health and care, receiving salary from a company, public services, municipalities/regional social services or even having a particular contract with the patient. Healthcare students that already play an active - and paid - role in hospitals may form part of this target group, according to the specifications of each project country's welfare system.
- **Informal caregivers:** With informal caregivers, one should refer to people that support in the care of their reference people but do not have a contract to execute this task such as family/relatives' carers.

5.4 ROLE OF FACILITATORS

The role of the **facilitator in each partner organisation involved in co-creation** is fundamental to ensure the effective and smooth organisation and implementation of the activities and events under T2.3. One facilitator is established by each partner, and she/he will be responsible for providing inputs for discussion and guiding stakeholders towards the inputs for the EU (d)HL Strategy. **The functions of facilitators include:**

- Responsibility of coordinating the identification/recruitment of the stakeholders;
- Coordinating/supervising all the logistics (meetings, invitations, reports, etc.);
- Overseeing the implementation of co-creation events/workshops and taking actions for their improvement / adjustment when necessary;
- Knowledge brokering - Maintaining dialogue and contact with the stakeholders and informing them about project progress and main results;
- Creating trust in the project and in the consortium and maintaining it for the entire duration of the activities;
- Coordinating communication and dissemination activities;
- Maintaining close connection with WP2 leader, T2.3 leader, and Coordinator;
- Reporting on the activities implemented and monitoring the proposed indicators;

- Guaranteeing the compliance to data privacy and ethics requirements.

To ensure good communication and exchange of knowledge and experiences within the stakeholders, the facilitator shall have:

✓ **Critical appraisal skills:** capacity to appraise evidence to evaluate its quality, importance, and applicability to a particular context. In addition to traditional critical appraisal skills, the facilitator should have a minimum knowledge of the sector, the broader environment, its key players, and controversies – and use this to gauge the applicability and adaptability of new evidence to users' contexts.

✓ **Communication skills:** strong oral and written communication skills. The facilitator should use active listening skills to gain insight into the interests, issues, and innovation of the co-creation members.

✓ **Mediation skills:** capacity to assemble teams and foster collaboration amongst individuals and groups who would not normally work together. The facilitator should be able to reconcile misunderstandings, facilitate the identification of shared goals, and negotiate mutually beneficial roles for all group members.

✓ **Previous relevant experience in facilitation processes and education:** it is recommended that the facilitator has some previous experience in education (formal/non-formal) and/or facilitation/coordination of teams or groups. They shall be able to work with people with different ages, cultures, backgrounds and to recognise the group's dynamics and behavioural styles and foster interaction and participation of all members.

Other important skills to be considered are, on one side, soft skills - flexibility, ability to create an inclusive environment, enthusiasm, active listening, time management, neutrality - and, on the other side, technical skills (especially qualitative data gathering), and facilitation skills.

Partners could appoint internal existing staff for the role of facilitator or hire new human resources to fulfil this profile and to carry out the activities using assigned personnel costs.

The appointed IDEAHL facilitator(s) for their co-creation activities are:

Partner	Facilitator(s)	Partner	Facilitator(s)
CSPA	Isabel Díez Valcarce Laura Pruneda González	CEI	Stefania Silvestri, Gabriele Migolla
SESPA HUCA		MLHSA	Lena Schulze
FICYT		UCN	Jacob Østergaard Madsen
CE	Michelle Perello, Beatrice Avagnina, Sara Amador	MDU	Karin Schölin Bywall, Therese Norgren
ISRAA	Adele De Stefani	SeAMK	Aino Alaverdyan, Katja Valkama, Mika Uitto and Merja Hoffrén-Mikkola
RMIT	María Gabriela Irrazabal, Kerryn Butler-Henderson	ADIPER	Manuel Gallardo
RMIT- EU		ALL DIGITAL	Claudia Matera, Alfonso Araujo
RMIT- UNI		CDC	Ângela Pinto
E-SENIORS	Romane Seas	EIWH	Rebecca Moore, Vanessa Moore

Table 4 - Appointed IDEAHL facilitator(s) for their co-creation activities

5.5 ETHICAL ASPECTS

IDEAHL project's nature of co-creation includes several types of data but mainly (d)HL and socio-economic related data gathered from the interactions with stakeholders. The consortium will comply with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 - General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and ethics procedures. The ethical standards and guidelines of GDPR and Horizon Europe will be applied and ethics approvals are requested when necessary in line with national requirements.

All participants (or legal tutors in case of children) involved in the co-creation process and the (d)HL Strategy of IDEAHL will be provided with an IDEAHL participant **Information sheet and Informed consent**. Each partner will have these documents available in their own language so that participants in their co-creation activities can be absolutely sure of what they are signing.

Customisable support templates for different target groups and different languages were developed and provided to partners by the Coordinator.

Participants will be informed of the rationale for the activity and what is being asked of them to make a fully informed decision about whether or not to participate in the co-creation process. Participation will be fully voluntary. In case that they participate, they must sign the Informed Consent. In the case of the participation of minors, their legal representatives must also sign it.

5.6 CO-CREATION PLANNING

5.6.1 INVITING AND RECRUITING PARTICIPANTS

The active participation of stakeholders is one of the most important factors for the project's success and effectiveness. Therefore, the facilitators and their teams shall invest in a thorough identification of potential participants and invitation and recruitment process. In the upcoming months, it is relevant to mention the following points:

o **Step 1: Define the participants' profile.** At the proposal stage, partners pre-selected their preferred target groups to work with in the co-creation. It is advisable to keep in mind some criteria for participants' recruitment and invitation:

- Number of participants depending on the targets set for each partner in the Grant Agreement. Ideally, partners shall try to invite more people than those expected to be able to tackle potential last-minute withdrawals.
- Demographic aspects such as the gender and age balance are not a prerequisite in the Grant Agreement, but they shall be considered whenever possible. Likewise, partners can seek to involve participants from different areas (e.g., cities and rural areas), cultures or ethnic background, as well as socially excluded groups and minorities to give the opportunity to every interested group to be represented.
- Finally, in principle, the people who will attend the events should be interested in doing so. Involving participants with strong interest or personal experience in the subject matter, could be a strong incentive and ensure engagement in the co-creation process.

o **Step 2: Prepare an initial information set in the local language (if necessary).** The starting point of communication with stakeholders shall be the preparation of specific information materials / social media posts in the local language and, if needed, providing them with the list

of pre-set questions on the research activities (Section 5.7). If partners do not want to create communication information from scratch, the materials produced in WP5 can be translated in national languages (e.g., leaflets and other approved visual materials can be handed out either in physical meetings or disseminated online).

o Step 3: Identify and engage multipliers. ‘Multipliers’, i.e., strategic stakeholders or local actors that have the capacity to reach out to a wide number of local individuals can be identified. The local multipliers should be approached directly, and efforts could be invested in engaging them into the project activities as participating stakeholders or at least as supporters e.g., by distributing information through their channels and inviting their contacts to join the activities.

> **Reach out through existing actors and channels.** For target groups’ identification and engagement, partners should rely on channels and actors that already exist in their areas. They are encouraged to rely on their own local experience. Furthermore, informal communication with the members of stakeholder groups would be very helpful, (i.e., simply asking them what the best way to reach out to their organisations/institutions is). In this sense, a strategy would be to identify ‘leaders’ – well-known and respected representatives of communities – and to invite them to the co-creation, since they can potentially reach other individuals, organisations and institutions.

> **Organise (onsite or online) Info Days.** Especially in the case of partners that have high stakeholder engagement targets to fulfil, the organisation of an Info Day could be interesting to attract a wider public prior to the start of co-creation activities. In the Info Day, they could provide detailed information about the project and the co-creation activities open to volunteering individuals of the target groups.

o Step 4: Attract and recruit volunteers from target groups. The first part of the dissemination strategy of facilitators and their teams shall cover the online community. Announcements about upcoming co-creation events shall be made in partners’ newsletters, institutional websites, and social media accounts to reach a maximum audience. For specific population cohorts, call for expression of interest to take part in the co-creation process can also be posted in specific locations, for instance schools, universities, doctors’ offices, or city halls. In parallel, partners can use direct contacts through emails and phone calls to targeted stakeholders and potential local multipliers. This will help to extend the dissemination reach, exploiting other pre-existing dedicated networks.

The recruitment will be accompanied by essential information regarding the project, the co-creation objectives, and structure. In certain cases, additional background material will also be provided (e.g., summary of the projects' findings, information regarding the co-creation methodology and tools) as thought-provoking material that will generate a common basis for the subject of the events.

Announcements of activities and/or invitations for participation will be sent with enough time so that people have spare days in their calendars. To enrol participants, voluntarily calls for expression of interest can be launched e.g., Google Form, digital Event Invitation, or open registration emails. In addition, people whose participation is essential can be contacted by phone.

Enrolment of target groups' volunteers shall happen, on average, **1 month before** the start of each co-creation event, so as to offer enough time for additional invitations to be sent in cases of limited participation. Facilitators can foresee a **reserve list** to reduce the risk of limited participation in case people fail to confirm their attendance in time. Organisers might also investigate the chance to offer 'rewards' to participants. In case such rewards exist, they will be mentioned in the invitation as they could act as additional motivation for participation.

Figure 4 - Planning & recruitment steps for traditional co-creation activities

5.6.2 GROUP-SPECIFIC RECOMMENDATIONS

Each project partner defined their own target groups at a proposal level based on their previous experience and links with local communities, professionals, and citizens. Having previously worked with the target groups shall be a preventive measure to ensure the recruitment runs smoothly and partners feel confident in dealing with their stakeholders.

Despite this, a number of tips and recommendations to support partners in the recruitment of their stakeholder groups have been gathered by WP2 Leader to further support the consortium in the recruitment phase. When necessary, partners will comply with their national ethical regulations for these tasks.

Seniors: For the recruitment of the senior group, facilitators might exploit the following channels among others: senior centres, healthcare centres, senior associations, universities of Third Age, gyms or other facilities organising courses/activities for seniors, etc. An effective way

to contact and motivate the elderly themselves to participate is to talk to them directly, through in-person meetings or by calling them, to present to them the project activities and answer their questions. Pre-existing contacts with seniors must also be exploited. Mobility issues should also be taken into account during the recruitment: thus, it is best to prioritise contacting seniors living close to the organisation's facilities, or to consider organising the discussion closer to them. In the case of recruiting seniors from care and retirement homes, one might consider relocating the activity directly in their premises.

People with migrant background: The most direct way to attract people with a migrant background could be reaching out to civil society organisations and other associations working with the target groups at regional/local level. Moreover, individual contact and invitation of professionals and experts who work on integration & migrants' education projects might represent a direct channel to reach additional people with migrant background. Social media posts and placement of leaflets in public places such as municipalities' halls & squares, cultural locals, pharmacies, doctors' offices, might also help to reach further participants.

Low-income citizens: Facilitators shall contact national/regional/local governmental offices and ask them to advertise the call for recruitment at their premises and among their networks. Another way could be the contact of NGOs, foundations, charities, and other associations working with low-income families. Facilitators might also take advantage of direct contact with colleagues as well as other external educators, trainers, health professionals working with disadvantaged population groups. Another option could be to identify relevant regional / local Low Income Assistance Initiatives and Programmes and contact the responsible persons to help with the target group's engagement.

People with low digital skills: For the recruitment of people with low digital skills, facilitators might exploit places such as schools/universities that provide digital training, support, or education to this specific target group. The dissemination of information for recruitment purposes shall be developed in paper format, for instance in the form of posters or leaflets or other visual materials to be posted or distributed on site. Secondary channels for

recruitment might be universities of the Third Age, day centres, local libraries or public centres running digital literacy classes for beginners, or any other place/event where people with low digital skills might go for support or education.

Children: Collaborating with schools could be the easiest route to recruit children. School can provide facilitators with the required number of participants, a classroom to organise the activities and they could guarantee that the same children would be available throughout the co-creation process if multiple activities and events are foreseen. Direct contacts with school teachers/directors with whom partners have pre-existing relations could be an effective way to fasten and facilitate the engagement process. Nevertheless, facilitators shall begin the planning of co-creation activities with such a target group in due time, take into account some difficulties that might arise from the recruitment process, such as communication delays due to long administrative procedures, holidays, exams periods. To widen the participation other methods could be exploited including:

- Dissemination of information across associations and NGOs, for instance the ones implementing Education to Global Citizenship initiatives, to share school contacts.
- Promotion across local-based associations organizing activities targeting children (e.g., after-school clubs, scout groups, oratories).
- Word of mouth through personal contacts with families with children.

Among children's groups, **minors with diabetes** are also expected to take part in IDEAHL co-creation. For their recruitment, beyond schools, other engagement ways could include contacts with health educators, doctors, diabetes care practices, as well as other medical clinics and hospitals, specialised networks and institutions working with diabetic families. Leaflets and flyers, personalised and tailored to the parents of diabetic children, could be used and disseminated in various locations: schools, general and specialist practitioners, pharmacies, diabetes clinics and other medical centres, etc. Additionally, facilitators might envisage to share announcement on diabetes-related or health-related websites and health insurance funds.

Young women: A very effective way for the recruitment of young women could be

partnering with youth centres and universities. There are often women's sports clubs, theatre, language, or painting clubs inside universities that can be good spaces for the recruitment of young women. NGOs networks working on gender issues and health clinics are good spaces too. Informative talks can be a useful tool with which it is possible to contact women's groups that can provide with participants. Facilitators shall also engage with young women through the platforms they are using, such as Instagram, LinkedIn. By publishing attractive posts and encouraging young people to share it, facilitators can call the attention of this group and motivate them to participate in their activities.

Pregnant women: Partners shall contact national/regional/local offices for birth and childhood and ask them to advertise the call for recruitment among their networks. Partners might also take advantage of direct contact with health professionals working in the 'mother and child' sector, inviting them to disseminate information among clients. Another way to recruit pregnant women could be to contact midwives' centres and associations, hospital, maternity care units that organise parental courses and/or parental groups, and dissemination of IDEAHL activities across mothers' associations. Face-to-face contact with pregnant women can be considered too. Reaching out to clients visiting a gynaecologist's study and mothers attending paediatrician's studies could also be considered useful methods for recruitment.

People with disabilities: For the recruitment of people with disabilities, facilitators shall contact local organisations and associations offering care and support to this specific target group. Depending on the location, there can be a variety of disability-related support groups, as well as local or regional rehabilitation or disability service centres. Additional channels of recruitment may be: senior organisations and local senior centres, social media groups and university programmes/departments for students with disabilities. Certain support groups may have mailing lists to send a recruiting announcement to, whereas many national and international organisations have regional contacts who can help find local participants. Engaging with people that work in close contact with disabled people, or are advocates, may provide additional networks. This is especially true for those that care for and communicate for non-verbal disabled people. Moreover, some people with disabilities are part of networks that actively share information: word of a positive experience can spread rapidly and result in

potential participants getting involved. It would be advisable to take advantage of this word-of-mouth recruiting, seeking out participants that are vocal members of a community, be it senior centres, disability support groups or even student organisations.

Health & care professionals and formal caregivers: To engage health and care professionals and formal carers, the most effective channel for recruitment is to reach an agreement with local public healthcare services, private/public hospitals, nursing homes, professionals' associations, and/or private companies that provide care services locally. The ideal situation would be to secure 2-3 health and care organisations that commit to engage a specific number of professionals and caregivers from their staff. Info days and in-person meetings could be arranged to secure these centres and/or recruit professionals directly. Relying on 'multipliers' and 'local leaders' can be strategic for the recruitment of these target groups. For instance, securing the support of a manager of health & care entities or a renowned health professional shall be exploited to reach further representatives of the target group. To complement these actions, other methods to recruit additional professionals could be also foreseen including profiling on social networks like LinkedIn or specialised magazines, attending local seminars/events, and not less importantly leveraging direct contacts.

Informal caregivers: To involve informal carers, the most effective mechanism is to contact Social Services Departments as they shall have registration for those entitled to receive different kind of support and they know their reference people. Facilitators could get in touch with sector managers, who through their social and professional networks would be able to provide contacts for recruitment. Another strategy can be to involve local associations of patients and caregivers and voluntary associations, which deal with the care of seniors and dependent persons. Moreover, facilitators could opt for online ways of recruitment. For instance, Facebook groups and pages dealing with informal care, such as Patient Centres or networks of family care givers could be identified.

It is worth reminding that definitions of formal and informal caregivers are provided in Section 5.2, so partners know whom they are expected to recruit under these target groups.

Healthcare students & lecturers: Universities will play a key role in the involvement of health professions students and academics/lecturers. Two dual actions could be taken to recruit students: at a formal level, by the institutions themselves, and through self-organised student collectives. As a first step, the facilitators could identify universities, meet with the didactic managers of the Medicine and Health Professions departments, and organise information seminars on the project. Co-designing could also be held in university spaces and supervised by the lecturers who talked to the facilitators. This participation could also be framed in courses or seminars, so that students can choose to participate in IDEAHL as a compensatory assignment. Another channel to consider could be dialogue with student representatives and student associations: facilitators could find their contacts on the universities' websites and association's' Facebook pages and schedule meetings to secure collaboration.

Policy makers: To engage policy makers, the first step shall be to investigate the policy areas to which the project research may provide useful insights. Thus, it would be advisable to map out the organisations and people with influence in those policy areas, considering aspects such as who makes the decision and who implements the policy. Social media is an effective and nowadays privileged tool to develop networks. In particular, Twitter provides insight into the conversations taking place on relevant topics and opportunities to interact with those interested/involved in the same issues or processes. In-presence networking events, however, should not be discarded to meet potential policy makers, tell them about the IDEAHL project, and seek to engage them in the co-creation.

Prisoners: For the recruitment of prisoners, it is essential to work in coordination with the people who work in the penitentiary centres: social educators, therapists, health professionals, etcetera. The security and confidentiality regulations of the prison must be rigorously complied with, so obtaining all the permits beforehand is the starting point of the co-creation activities with this target group. In a second phase, consideration should be given to selecting the least dangerous modules and adapting the recruitment campaign, preferably in person, given the absence of audio-visual media.

5.6.3 LOGISTICS & RESOURCES

To organise traditional co-creation activities, partners will need to think of:

5.6.3.1 Location

The ‘space’ (either physical or digital) where to implement the participatory activities is a factor to be considered.

When selecting the physical venue of the co-creation activities, partners will need to ensure they have a safe and accessible space for co-creation, which could include their same premises but also other types of locations such as renting a dedicated room with the right conditions or benefitting from schools’ and municipality’s spaces, as well as facilities of a long-term partner organisation active with the target group at local/regional level, etc. Partners shall consider several aspects that may require the physical space to have certain characteristics. In general, co-creation activities will be organised in the most suitable setting which shall have a proper balance among the features presented below:

- ✓ Availability of appropriate technical infrastructure.
- ✓ Sufficient space to hold the number of participants as well as for the selected methods to be performed optimally.
- ✓ Appropriate lighting and adequate air circulation and temperature.
- ✓ Enough wall space or freestanding surfaces for hanging posters so they can be seen by all participants.
- ✓ Quiet and safe place.
- ✓ Easy access and proximity to public transport. In particular, for seniors, partners should consider a location that is close and easy to where seniors live and for people with disabilities, partners need to make sure the setting is equipped to be accessed by any recruited participant including for wheelchair users.

In addition to the main space, depending on the group’s needs, event venues may have an extra space or room that can be used in case the participants are divided in subgroups. Lunch or coffee breaks may be served to avoid participants’ fatigue especially for activities whose length will be more than one hour.

When selecting the right digital platform for the co-creation activities, partners shall take into account different aspects to ensure a smooth, safe, and reliable experience of participants online:

- ✓ Availability of appropriate IT infrastructure and stable Wi-Fi connection not to experience connection problems;
- ✓ Selection of the most suitable platform which the partner is familiar with and taking into account the number of people hosted and the digital features available;
- ✓ Consider using a platform that allows to split groups into different “online rooms” for events with a large number of participants;
- ✓ Consider having one or more breaks during the online co-creation session, depending on the duration of the activity;
- ✓ It is recommended that partners use a tool that allows to admit manually participants like Teams or Zoom to ensure that only registered attendees connect.

5.6.3.2 Calendar and materials

An internal calendar should be agreed on time to organise the different activities and organise activities in due time. The most suitable time slots for co-creation activities shall be ensured to attract more people, which will depend greatly on the local context including public holidays, hours of meals, etc.

Upon the definition of the co-creation activities calendar, each IDEAHL partner is requested to communicate - by email - the fixed dates and location for co-creation to Task Leader 2.3 ISRAA and WP2 Leader CE at least 2 weeks in advance.

Regarding materials, **consumables for physical co-creation activities** may be also needed e.g., pens, post-its, blank sheets, dashboard, etc. according to the chosen co-creation methods. In general, partners will make sure that the required material is available at the time and place of the events.

Finally, one shall consider that the project must be promoted during the co-creation events mandatorily. In physical events partners can showcase **promotional materials** such as roll-ups and posters and/or distribute leaflets. For online co-creation activities, the digital version of the poster can be shown and/or the website and social media. Depending on the target group and

their level of digital literacy, a QR code might be also facilitated to participants in both online and onsite events to consult IDEAHL website or digital promotional resources.

For both online and onsite events, it is strongly recommended to foresee a **short introductory presentation of the IDEAHL project in the event programme or at least to share, in advance, preliminary information about the project to the registered participants.**

5.6.3.3 Signature lists and proofs of events

Partners will need to remember to keep records and proofs of their events at their premises for transparency reasons and future potential audits by the EU Commission. For each activity partners will need to prepare to **record the participation of the attending persons and collect evidence:**

- ✓ Prepare signature lists that must be signed in onsite events;
- ✓ Keep records of participants in online events according to established ethics and confidentiality procedures e.g., report of connected participants downloaded from the used online platform, screenshot of the list of participants, registration of the meeting via web tools such as Webropol, Microsoft, etc.
- ✓ Take pictures/videos of the physical venue, of the facilitators managing the activities, and if permitted, of the participants. If participants are shown in pictures or videos, they must have been informed in advance of the collection and the processing of the information. This can be included in the Informed consent form and signature list participants will sign. Further information in this regard is included in Section 5.11 - Dissemination.

Partners must always ensure to respect the privacy of the participants. Signature lists will be stored in a secured place at each partner's premises according to relevant regulations on data protection. Signature lists will not be shared within the consortium, nor checked by the WP2 responsible partners. They will be kept inside each organisation. Regarding pictures and videos clearly showing participants' faces, these will be disseminated only if the partners have the consent of the participants to publicly share such audio-visual materials.

5.7 CO-CREATION IMPLEMENTATION

5.7.1 OVERVIEW

Section 5.7 provides partners with a roadmap for the execution of the IDEAHL traditional co-creation activities. The list of defined research questions to collect stakeholders' feedback is also provided below. In addition, common co-creation methods and tools are offered to harmonise the implementation of the activities in all project countries. Based on this framework, each facilitator should adjust or adapt the execution of co-creation according to their plans for the co-creation events (e.g., number, duration, type), as well as according to the number of members of target groups, their level of preparation, knowledge, and commitment.

Partners involved in the co-creation process will have to organise at least two sessions to engage different population cohorts from February to July 2023, build their trust and thus facilitate knowledge brokerage either offline or online. The facilitator will be responsible for the smooth running of the activities and the communication with WP/Task leaders and the Coordinator. The first compulsory co-creation activity will be devoted to gather initial feedbacks on (d)HL and identify barriers and areas of improvement for the project's EU Strategy. In the second event, stakeholders shall define more in detail the types of potential interventions on (d)HL and reflect on social/ethics implications and further specifications related to (d)HL. Furthermore, partners are free (and encouraged) to promote complementary actions to ensure the maximum feedback is collected from all involved stakeholders and ensure all of them have enough chances to provide their views. Complementary feedback can be retrieved through offline work e.g., requesting written feedback to research questions. Guidance on this process is provided in section 5.7.4.

Concerning the structure of the co-creation sessions, the activities should be developed with a sense of progress in which the different sessions are linked together, following a logical order. The most common structure, and the one that will be the basis for IDEAHL co-creation activities, is a three-phase structure, portrayed in the figure below. This structure will be adapted to the specific objectives and tools of each co-creation event, but in most cases, it will boil down to the same line of activities.

Figure 5 – Structure of co-creation sessions

Before the co-creation process takes place, the subject matter of the project, of the co-creation sessions, and of the IDEAHL Strategy will be clearly presented to participants. In addition, during the first co-creation session, short presentations (e.g., slides, videos) will be made. Alternatively, relevant materials and information can be provided to participants beforehand. It is advisable that the list of research questions is shared in advance so that participants can familiarise themselves with the concepts that will be addresses during the co-creation activities.

During the first co-creation activity, participants shall get to know each other before starting collaborative activities. Examples of ice-breaker activities to allow participants to connect with each other are presented in the following paragraphs. After the introduction, the main sessions - co-creativity phase and evaluation phases - will be carried out. The core phase is the one in which innovative ideas and concepts are generated from the collaboration and discussion of the participants. The methods and techniques to be applied in this phase are also indicated in the following paragraphs. Then, typically, the co-creation sessions should end with a short final discussion in which each participant, or the groups that have been formed, get to say what their key findings during the day were. These findings should be assessed in terms of feasibility, potential and correspondence with the needs, concerns, and trends of the target group involved.

Beyond the co-creation sessions in each project country, under T2.3, it is planned that a panel of (d)HL experts is established and mobilised online by ISRAA, CE, and CSPA to gather input and endorsement for the development of the IDEAHL Strategy. Experts will be retrieved when the WP1 analysis is finished and contacted to contribute to the project.

5.7.2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on the results of T2.2, the knowledge of partners, and the work carried out until now under the IDEAHL project, a comprehensive list of research questions has been defined by the project and is reported below. Partners will address these questions to their target groups' representatives, collect and report the generated feedback and ideas to help build the IDEAHL Strategy. According to their target groups, **partners shall be free to adapt the questions** or decide to omit specific ones that might be particularly challenging for their groups' representatives. Partners working with children, whose number - however - is very limited in the IDEAHL co-creation exercise, shall be given greater freedom in the adaptation of the research questions. Questions can be more limited in number and simplified. These partners might consider asking the more complex questions to the parents/legal tutors of the involved children.

List of questions for co-creation:

Topic	Questions	Instructions / guidelines
Introductory questions	How often do you search for health-related information on the Internet?	<p>The aim of this first set of questions is to introduce participants into the discussion and investigate (d)HL behaviours.</p> <p>3 main questions have been proposed to be common to all partners, but facilitators shall be free to discuss additional interesting aspects that might emerge from the discussion.</p> <p><u>A question specifically on what is (d)HL is not included because it is assumed partners have introduced this concept at the start of (or prior to) the first co-creation session.</u> However, if the facilitators prefer, such a question can be raised at the opening of the first co-creation session. For (d)HL definition, partners must refer to WP1 deliverable (D1.1).</p>
	Which kind of digital tools you use to search for this information? E.g., mobile phone, health-related app, etc.?	
	When you search for health-related information online, do you do it alone or with others? If you do it with other people, what type of relationship do you have with them (family, friends, colleagues, caregivers)?	
	Do you feel comfortable in searching for health-related information on digital tools, understanding it, and using it for your own life and health management?	
	Do you usually look for information on the internet about other aspects of your life?	

<p>Specific domains of (d)HL strategy</p>	<p>What, in your opinion, are the general barriers that society faces regarding (d)HL?</p>	<p>Depending on the target group, partners should be able to ensure a debate on barriers & areas of improvement to come up with barriers and areas of improvements for (d)HL in relation to the Strategy’s domains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health promotion. • Disease prevention. • Treatment & self-care. <p>If target groups are more experienced e.g., healthcare professionals and policy makers, partners could specifically ask to list barriers and areas of improvement in relation to each of the domains of the Strategy.</p> <p>For people without a dedicated healthcare background/experience, it might be more difficult to relate concepts to each domain. Therefore, it will be up to the facilitators to promote a debate (see facilitation methods in Section 5.8) and retrieve the answers and associate them with the domains. Partners might also consider guiding the discussion by providing themselves examples of barriers and areas of improvements through the presentation of WP1 and/or T2.2 outcomes in this regard. This might represent a starting point to “break the ice” and encourage exchange of ideas to end up with stakeholders’ own ideas (or validation of WP1/T2.2 results).</p>
	<p>What are your personal barriers to (d)HL?</p>	
	<p>What do you see as the main areas for improvement concerning (d)HL?</p>	
<p>Interventions on (d)HL</p>	<p>Do you recognise you have participated in any initiatives on the subject of HL or (d)HL?</p> <p>If you do, what has worked and what has not?</p>	<p>It is important to investigate whether participants have ever felt they have participated in (d)HL interventions. If they do, it shall be asked what was successful and what was not.</p>
	<p>How could healthcare providers support you in (d)HL?</p>	
	<p>How could policy makers support you in (d)HL?</p>	<p>It is important to investigate the tailored perceptions and suggestions of each group of stakeholders regarding the areas of improvements, which will be later considered for the WP2 IDEAHL Strategy and WP4 work. It is important that partners</p>

		investigate these research questions from the point of view of both healthcare providers and policy makers, due to the requirements of WP2 and WP4.
	Which should be the key elements to consider when designing healthcare interventions for your group in our IDEAHL EU Strategy?	It is important that partners foster discussion and brainstorming to collect suggestions for the Strategy's interventions of WP3. This question is especially crucial for policy makers, healthcare professionals, caregivers, and healthcare students. It might be more challenging for other groups, so partners shall be free to adapt it and use facilitation tools and supporting materials to promote debate.
	Examples of potential specific interventions/measures that could be useful to improve your (d)HL skills for: Health promotion Disease prevention Treatment & self-care	Partners should collect at least 1 example per domain. The examples and domain can emerge from the discussion and brainstorming, promoted through dedicated facilitation tools, without posing a direct question in relation to each that might inhibit the answers. Partners can also consider guiding the discussion by providing themselves examples of potential interventions and assess those with the stakeholders to improve or change them. In such cases, <u>examples of potential interventions, for each domain, are reported in Section 3 as a result of T2.2. Also, partners can find examples in the Grant Agreement at page 107.</u>
	Are you aware of any successful or less successful interventions, policies, measures, programmes to support (d)HL?	Although relevant for IDEAHL research purposes, this question is rather specific, thus, it is recommended to be posed only to healthcare professionals / formal caregivers, healthcare students, and policy makers.
Ethics / Social Implications	Do you think gender affects the level of (d)HL among citizens?	A few questions investigating ethics and social aspects have been planned due to the fact that co-creation inputs must also feed the work of WP4 and the future releases of the IDEAHL WP4 Ethics and Inclusion Toolkit. Partners shall be free to adapt these questions and foresee additional ones if the discussion is interesting for their target groups. Such questions might be difficult to pose to children, so they might be omitted in this case. It might be helpful to make examples of "vulnerable conditions", so that participants can understand what
	Do you think people in vulnerable conditions [<i>make examples according to your target group e.g., migrants, people with disabilities, people with low socio-economic status</i>] are more likely to experience difficulties in (d)HL?	

		is meant. Examples and inputs in this regard can be retrieved from D4.1. If partners work with vulnerable groups, they can further adapt/expand the question.
Specific questions	Foresee additional questions as per requirements set in the co-creation table of the IDEAHL Grant Agreement.	In the Grant Agreement (pages 103-104), there are reported complementary pieces of information that each partner shall ask to their target groups. This information changes from partner to partner and was set at the time of the proposal preparation. Partners are advised to revise such information and decide what is still relevant to be asked to stakeholders. In addition, partners might want to ask any other specific questions, but always taking into account timeframes and preferences of target groups in question.

5.7.3 CO-CREATION EXECUTION

First (compulsory) co-creation session

Objective of the activity	<p>Present IDEAHL project and inform the target groups' members about (d)HL definition and trends in their country/Europe.</p> <p>Present specific challenges and objectives of the IDEAHL co-creation activities, the Strategy to develop, and introduce the list of research questions.</p> <p>Introduce participants one with another and create the basis for an effective and positive collaboration.</p> <p>Gather initial feedback on 1. Introductory questions + 2. Specific domains of (d)HL Strategy.</p>
Type of event and logistical details	<p><i>Suggested duration: half a day.</i></p> <p>The event should gather the selected representatives of the target groups. This activity shall be ideally presented as the first session of a longer discussion which will finalise during the following workshop and, possibly, optional additional offline work and collaboration. Partners should provide physical or digital space for the organisation of the event and draft the agenda.</p> <p>Standard programme:</p> <p>(1) presentation of project achievements and activities as well as the programme and objectives of the co-creation process; (2) introduction of participants using one or more "ice-breaker" techniques (see Section 5.8); (3) core phase to discuss the first 2 sets of research</p>

	<p>questions (Introductory questions + Specific domains of (d)HL strategy questions)*; (4) evaluation and assessment phase during which the ideas and concepts emerged from the core session are evaluated and assessed by participants.</p> <p><i>* If partners want to assess some questions in the following event, or foresee more questions in the current one, they can adapt the approach as long as the overall outcome of the co-creation experience is to collect all needed input.</i></p>
Expected number of attendants	Depending on the needs of each partner. However, it is suggested to hold sessions with no more than 20-30 attendants. The number of participants will also depend on the experience of the partner in facilitation/co-creation activities, the chosen space / modality, etc.
Expected results	<p>Introduce project and participants.</p> <p>Collect feedback about 1. Introductory questions & 2. Specific domains of (d)HL.</p> <p>Reporting of the session by filling out T2.3 report template and send it to ISRAA within 1 week of time after the last co-creation session.</p>
Suggestions	<p>A facilitator is needed to foster debate and at least one assistant to support the facilitator with administrative tasks and to collect all suggestions coming from participants.</p> <p>If possible, partners shall foresee a coffee break and/or lunch to avoid participants' fatigue.</p> <p>It is advisable to share the list of research questions and preliminary information about the IDEAHL project prior to the first co-creation session. This allows facilitators to gather feedback from participants before the event and determine their level of familiarity with digital tools and online health information. If the time is not enough to discuss all planned questions, offline work by stakeholders might be foreseen e.g., replying to questions in written form, or in a shared document prior to the following session.</p>
Date	Partners have freedom to organise their events during the period of February and July 2023, according to their preferences and needs. However, it is suggested that the first activity takes place during Spring 2023 (February – April 2023).
To do list	Identify the venue / modality of the activity > Set dates and draft programme > Inform WP2 Task & WP leader > Send out invitations and disseminate activity > Make sure to have all informed consent signed prior to activity start > Share background information and list of research questions.
Main monitoring indicators	<p>Quantitative: number of participants, number of ideas validated at the end of the session.</p> <p>Qualitative: satisfaction questionnaire handed out to participants; level of engagement perceived by facilitators.</p>

Second (compulsory) co-creation session

Objective of the activity	<p>Present the ideas gathered in the first co-creation event.</p> <p>Gather remaining feedback on the 3 last sets of research questions and come to shared conclusions for the IDEAHL Strategy.</p> <p>Discuss any potential unsolved/unclear points emerged or missing from the first activity.</p>
Type of event and logistical details	<p><i>Suggested duration: half a day / one day, depending on partners' needs</i></p> <p>The event should gather the selected representatives of the target groups. Possibly, the same participants of the previous activity should attend this second event. Partners should provide physical/digital space for the organisation of the event and draft the agenda.</p> <p>Standard programme: (1) presentation of the key outcomes of the first co-creation workshop; (2) input collection about the last 3 sets of questions (Interventions questions; Ethics & Social Implications questions; Additional specific questions) *; (3) Final agreement on key concepts to transmit to the IDEAHL consortium for the Strategy development.</p> <p><i>* If partners want to assess some questions in the previous event, or foresee more questions in the current one, they can adapt the approach as long as the overall outcome of the co-creation experience is to collect all needed input.</i></p>
Expected number of attendants	<p>Depending on the needs of each partner. However, it is suggested to hold sessions of about 20-30 attendants. This will also depend on the experience of the partner in facilitation/co-creation activities, the chosen space / modality, etc.</p>
Expected results	<p>Finalise debates and idea generation on the list of research questions.</p> <p>Agree on main conclusions to be considered for the Strategy.</p> <p>Partners will have to finalise the T2.3 report template and send it to ISRAA within 1 week of time after the last co-creation session.</p>
Suggestions	<p>A facilitator and back-up persons are needed to foster debate and manage the groups.</p> <p>If possible, partners shall foresee a coffee break and/or lunch to avoid participants' fatigue.</p> <p>Optionally, partners can foresee some offline work by stakeholders, e.g., replying to questions in written form, or in a shared document, etc. prior or after the second session.</p> <p>Partners who do not want to stick to the traditional model have the option of using a more innovative format. For example, the strategy can be presented as if it was a new policy to be implemented, asking participants to represent different types of stakeholders and to negotiate among themselves how to modify the strategy so that it can be approved.</p>

Date	Partners have freedom to organise their events during the period of February and July 2023, according to their preferences and needs. However, it is suggested that the second activity ideally takes place within April-June 2023. At least, partners should plan their last session not so late in time compared to the first one in order not to lose the motivation of participants.
To do list	Identify the venue / modality of the activity > Set dates and draft programme > Inform WP2 Task & WP leader > Send out invitations to all previous participants with informed consent signed > Disseminate activity > If needed, share further background information and list of research questions.
Main monitoring indicators	Quantitative: number of participants, number of ideas validated at the end of the session. Qualitative: satisfaction questionnaire handed out to participants; level of engagement perceived by facilitators.

Incentives & prizes

Incentives or other rewards may be foreseen to recompense participants for their time and efforts in participating in the co-creation sessions. In addition, the use of prizes might be considered to garner competition and thus stimulate completion and encourage innovation (Ind et al., 2020; Benson et al., 2021). Peer-voting might be envisaged, and prizes can be awarded at the end of the co-creation experience. Following this approach, prizes can be given, for instance, to the most active participant, the users with the most realistic and practical ideas, the most creative ideas, the most thoughtful comments, etc.

5.7.4 ADDITIONAL (OPTIONAL) INPUT COLLECTION EFFORT

Considering the high number of people to involve, it is suggested to IDEAHL partners to complement the feedback retrieved from the T2.3 “traditional co-creation sessions” with additional efforts and approaches. This is advisable to retrieve the maximum input possible from target groups’ representatives. Partners shall be free to voluntarily opt and adapt these additional efforts according to their needs, preferences, and previous experience. A series of approaches are, however, proposed below.

Offline (written) feedback. The list of research questions can be shared among co-creation participants *ante/post* co-creation sessions. Although this depends on the type of stakeholders involved, it is advised to share the list of questions prior to the start of the co-creation to allow

people to familiarise with the topics and to know the contribution that it is expected from them. In-between and after the sessions partners can encourage participants to provide further written feedback. Written feedback can be also useful when retrieved from people that are shy or prefer to take more time to think and reply.

Shared working document(s), online community platforms. For the target groups with good digital literacy levels, another option could be to share an online working document with the list of research questions or complementary content that partners want to investigate more in-depth. This can be done via Teams, Google Drive, Dropbox, according to the partners' preferences and their GDPR policies. Furthermore, if partners are used to working with established collaborative platforms & forums such as Moodle, Miro, Trello, Samepage or Jamboard, they could exploit them to share research questions and ask participants to connect and share their views and opinions. In such cases, it is advisable that the facilitator(s) checks on the platform at least once daily, to ensure that individuals are participating, prompt discussion where necessary, and provide support and help with technical issues. The presence of a facilitator online can help to foster engagement, encourage discussion, and ensure that progress proceeds on time.

Survey, polls, Q&As, quizzes. Small surveys might be planned to ask specific feedback from participants to help design the Strategy and its priorities. CE will be in charge of creating and launching an English-based IDEAHL EU survey, which can be translated by partners and shared among their co-creation participants. In addition, it is worth mentioning some creative and entertaining platforms that can be used for Q&As, quizzes and polls, such as [Slido](#), [Kahoot](#) or [Mentimeter](#). These tools might be used both during the co-creation sessions to keep the event more dynamic and for follow-up, offline activities. These platforms can be helpful to get everyone involved, in case participants feel shy or prefer to reply anonymously. This is also useful to build a safe environment and allow everyone to be heard.

Individual interviews or calls. Individual interviews or calls might also be planned by partners to retrieve more feedback from participants. If this was the case, it is recommended that partners schedule them at a convenient time for participants and they keep them rather short asking very direct and simple questions.

Cultural probes to collect qualitative feedback. Cultural probes are an approach to support qualitative user research and consist of prompts, questions, and instructions along with artifacts

for recording thoughts and feelings. Their purpose is to elicit thoughts, opinions, and feelings on a range of topics. If cultural probes are used, it is advisable to follow these steps:

- Define the questions and design the probe(s). These can take many forms. They can be on paper, online, or on a mobile device, you choose. Simple is best from. Determine the frequency that you want subjects to record their activities/thoughts.
- Write short, simple questions that you want answered.
- Sketch the layout of the probe on a sheet of paper, ordering the questions, and leaving spaces for responses.
- Prototype and try-out the probe within the team. Optimise the design to make it accessible and attractive, this makes using it easier and better results will be gathered.
- Test your probe with trial participants, ask them to trial it for a day or two and give you feedback.
- Incorporate the initial feedback in final design revisions.
- Brief your subjects. Explain how to use the probe, how to contact you in case of questions, how to return the completed probe, etc.
- Follow up after the probe period has ended, schedule follow-up interviews with participants if needed.
- File the completed probes as a record and report key feedback emerged in the dedicated T2.3 report.

For further information, partners might want to consult the Cultural Probes Toolkit of the Erasmus+ [socialUP project](#).

5.8 CO-CREATION METHODS AND TOOLS

Facilitators will be able to use the **co-creation methods and tools** defined in the present document. In general, the choice of the sessions' methods will be subject to finding a balance between the following criteria:

- ✓ The objectives of the co-creation session,
- ✓ The core topic of the session and its content,
- ✓ The type of information the organiser wants to obtain as per the guidelines in the previous section,
- ✓ The participants' group,

- ✓ The time available,
- ✓ The venue/modality of the activity,
- ✓ The level of knowledge and training that the participants need for using the method,
- ✓ The availability of resources and materials required to implement each method.

The applied methods will be aided by structured procedures and visual techniques that can further help participants to communicate and rationalise their ideas. The IDEAHL approach for the **selection of tools and techniques is based on issues that have been proved as key methods of success by WP2 Leader and partners in similar activities, as well as in a number of previous EU funded projects - IC-Health, CIPTEC, RURITAGE, and SOCATEL.** It is worth noting that the list is not exhaustive, and partners can envisage other types of co-creation games and tools with which they may be more familiar.

The proposed methods are intended to be transversal due to IDEAHL's wide range of target groups, possibly with different characteristics and needs; such methods can be adjusted by partners based on their long-term experience in working with the selected target groups. Most stakeholders involved in the project will be adult population groups, and only a small number of participants will be minors. In the latter case, the responsible partners may make use of materials and facilitation approaches from familiar and educational contexts and can collaborate with parents, healthcare professionals or teachers to adjust the proposed methods. If needed, facilitators can evaluate with CE and ISRAA the most suitable co-creation methods to employ for their target groups.

To obtain the desired results, traditional co-creation activities shall allow adequate time for the applied co-creation tools to be performed properly. However, the duration of the sessions shall be kept within reasonable limits so that it is not a deterrent for participation. To this end, facilitators will ensure that predefined time limits are maintained, allowing everything to be adequately addressed and preventing any unforeseen delays in the overall duration. Also, by establishing a schedule for each activity and allowing breaks between them, the facilitators will avoid fatigue among the participants.

5.8.1 METHODS FOR INTRODUCTION PHASE

In co-creation activities it is important that participants connect one with another. After the introduction of the project, activities, and goals of the co-creation activity, an **'ice-breaker'**

exercise should follow to introduce participants to each other. Such an exercise is intended to help participants begin the process of forming themselves into a team and warm up the group. Organisers will clearly determine beforehand the information each participant needs to know (e.g. name, profession, experience in the field, reasons for attending, aspirations from participation, etc.). A list of common ice-breaker games, which can be used for in-person and/or online sessions, are presented below.

Standard personal introductions (30 seconds to 1 minute per person)

In-person / online session

A display board (physical or digital) can be prepared with information that participants will need to know e.g., name, age, where they are from, occupation, etc. Each participant will write down their details on the board. Afterwards, each participant reads out his/her personal details to the rest of the group. The display board can remain accessible/visible throughout the whole session. The purpose of this ice-breaker is to get to know participants. With defined criteria one can ensure that everyone gives and receives the same basic information.

Variable

Each person gives their name, where they are from and one other fact about themselves. This third fact could be freely chosen by each individual or the facilitator could suggest a theme.

Materials needed

Display board, flipchart, and marker pens for onsite events.

Online interactive board e.g., Mural or Jamboard for online events.

Name games (15 minutes)

In-person / online session

One participant starts by saying an adjective starting with the same letter as their first name, followed by their first name, for example “Kind Karen”, then, this person throws the (imaginary or real) ball to the next person, who will have to repeat the first participant’s adjective and name, and then add their own (e.g. hello Kind Karen, I’m Rich Rachel). If the ball hits the ground, the game will have to start again. The game will end when all participants have had the ball.

Material needed

A ball for onsite events (not compulsory).

Pair introduction interviews / “speed dating” game (1-2minutes per person)

In-person session

Participants pair up with another person they do not know. One person interviews the other for 1-2 minutes, then roles are swapped. Questions could include the reasons why the person is there and what they are hoping to learn or achieve. Then the whole group gathers together, and participants introduce their partner to the others, giving as much detail as they can remember. The rationale behind this is to “stir” the group and to provide a more personal connection and deeper understanding between the participants.

A variation of this method could be the “speed dating” game in which participants are divided in pairs and are required to switch partners after a very limited time frame in order to learn from each other. The facilitator can set a set of short specific questions to help participants introduce themselves.

Material needed

Paper sheets and pens for taking down notes if needed by participants.

The ball of string (20-30 minutes)

In-person session

This is an exercise that helps participants to introduce themselves and learn the names of the other members of the group. Participants form a circle. The facilitator takes a ball of string, holds onto the end of string and says his/her name and without letting go of the string, throws the ball to another person in the circle. The person who catches the ball says his/her name, holds onto the string and then throws the ball to another participant. This sequence is repeated until everybody in the circle is holding onto part of the string and a web has been formed. Once the web is formed, there is also a reflection of the implications of the collective task. The person who ended up with the ball of string passes it back to the person who threw it calling that person’s name and so on and the ball of string ends up complete again.

Materials needed

A ball of string.

People bingo (20-30 minutes)

In-person session

The facilitator writes down a list of questions that each person in the group will ask the other participants. The question can be specific to the session or generic. Each person should only ask one question to one person then find somebody else to introduce themselves to and ask another question. When they have found answers to all their questions, they say bingo and finish. Ten questions get people well mixed, and a lot of information shared.

Materials needed

Paper sheets, pens.

Mural ice-breaker games (20-30 minutes)

Online session

MURAL offers many options (<https://www.mural.co/blog/virtual-meeting-ice-breakers>) to allow participants to introduce themselves and get to know each other. Most used ones are:

1) "Where in the world are you?"

Participants can indicate on a virtual and shared map where they live, describe their city/town and something funny or iconic about it.

2) "What is your favourite film, tv series or book?" (<https://www.mural.co/templates/team-bookshelf>)

On a shared virtual bookshelf participants can introduce themselves and give a short pitch for their favourite film, book, or TV series.

3) "What are your favourite foods?" (<https://www.mural.co/templates/team-feast>)

On a shared digital template participants can describe one dish they love, and what it means to them. This might be an easy way to get people talking, offering insight into people's personal history, likes and dislikes.

4) "Show and tell" (<https://www.mural.co/templates/show-and-tell>)

Participants can pick an item (for instance, a picture) they wish to show to the others and spend a couple of minutes to describe its funny back-story. To make it more visually entertaining, it is possible to use the MURAL dedicated template. It would be advisable, for this game, to have all meeting attendees submit photos before the meeting starts.

Conceptboard ice-breaker games (20-30 minutes)

Online session

Like Mural, also on Conceptboard (<https://conceptboard.com/>) every game is shareable via a link and the sign up is only needed for who hosts the games, and it is for free. Two popular games are:

1) "Quick questions" (<https://app.conceptboard.com/board/yaec-gb4m-k2b1-yr5g-x76p>)

Participants open the template via a link with the pre-prepared questions. Everyone adds their answers on sticky notes. E.g.: What is your name?

2) "Choose your favourite" <https://app.conceptboard.com/board/za3f-o6bi-itxe-mxyt-zff3>

Participants choose among two or more options. This game might be useful for participants to start knowing each other more and break the ice with fun questions.

5.8.2 METHODS FOR CORE CO-CREATION PHASE

After the introduction, the second stage of the session can take place. This stage constitutes the **core co-creativity session** of the activity, and it is the phase in which the **innovative concepts will be developed**. A selection of appropriate method(s) that stimulate creative thinking and encourage participation are strongly recommended. Typically, this stage will start with a description of the IDEAHL project by the facilitator, followed by a description of the method(s) applied, making sure that all participants have understood how it works and what is expected of them.

Proposed co-creation techniques is presented below, offering an overview of each method, contexts of use, implementation guidelines, and requirements in terms of material and time.

Brainstorming (30-40 minutes)

In-person / online session

Brainstorming stimulates creative thinking and helps gather many ideas from the group (or sub-groups). When a brainstorming session starts, the objectives of the session should be clearly stated to all participants. Facilitators can allow everyone time to write down or think of some ideas (either alone or divided in sub-groups). Afterwards, each person/sub-group expresses an idea or thought, and this information is recorded. When using brainstorming, it is recommended to set a time limit.

Main features:

- ✓ Research questions are clearly explained to participants and presented in written form so that they are visible throughout the exercise. Questions can also be shared before the co-creation activity.
- ✓ The rules of the game are explained.
- ✓ All ideas are accepted. No criticism is allowed of any idea put forward.
- ✓ A timescale is set for the brainstorming session.
- ✓ Dedicated people can be given the task of noting the ideas down to be visible to the group/sub-group.
- ✓ When the time limit is up, ideas are analysed and conclusions made.
- ✓ The display board can be used as a resource to initiate the use of other planning tools.

Recommendations

Participants need to feel free to express their opinions. They must comply with the rules of the game: to avoid more than one person talking at the same time, the facilitator can have participants take turns to make their contribution. This reduces the risk of losing valuable ideas or opinions and allows all members to participate.

Participants will need time to warm up.

Materials needed

Flip chart, pens, and cards for onsite sessions.

Dedicated digital tool to gather ideas such as Mural, Jamboard, or simply an online shared document for online sessions.

World Café (multiple consecutive sessions of 15-20 minutes each)

In-person / online session

The World Café is a creative process for facilitating collaborative dialogue and the sharing of knowledge and ideas in a relatively short time (from a few hours up to one day workshop). A World Café setting needs to be created where participants discuss about an issue in small groups around café tables (or digital rooms if the session is held online). At regular intervals the participants move to a new table/room.

How it is used

- ✓ Participants explore an issue by discussing for multiple consecutive sessions.
- ✓ Participants shall ideally work in groups of 5-7 people.
- ✓ One of the participants is chosen as the host of the table/room.
- ✓ The whole group (except the table host) change tables/rooms after each session to 'cross-fertilise' their discussions with the ideas generated at other tables.
- ✓ After several minutes all participants of each table/room join another group, except for one participant who remains to brief the next group on what the last group has discussed. The participants that leave their table carry key ideas, themes, and questions into their new conversations.
- ✓ By providing opportunities for people to move in several rounds of conversation, ideas, questions, and themes will be linked and connected. At the end of the second or third round, all the tables/rooms will have been cross-pollinated with insights from prior conversations.

Each round is prefaced with a question developed for the specific context and desired purpose of the World Café. The same questions can be used for more than one round, or they can be built upon each other to focus the conversation or guide its direction. After three or more rounds, the whole group gathers to share and explore emerging insights and concepts, which are captured on flipcharts or by other means. At this point the Café may end and it could be concluded with a final plenary session, where the key ideas and conclusions are established.

Recommendations

The procedure of the method should be clearly explained. Questions to be discussed must be thought out and clear to engage participants. People should be reminded to record key ideas, draw thoughts, ideas and questions on the flipcharts that are used as tablecloths. The basic process is simple, but complexities of context, participants

and question definition make the presence of an experienced moderator necessary.

Material needed

Tables, flipchart paper or paper placemats for covering the tables, multi-coloured markers on each table, boards for posting the flipchart papers for onsite sessions.

Digital rooms for online sessions, user-friendly digital boards/tools for collecting ideas such as Mural or Jamboard.

Role-playing (one or two hours)

In-person / online session

The main goal of role-playing is to make an idea or a scenario tangible enough to elicit a response from participants. It helps to understand a subject in more depth, and it also stimulates creativity. It is easier to implement in in-person settings; however, if it is well studied and guided by an experienced facilitator, it also may be applied to digital environments.

How it is used

- ✓ An idea or scenario that needs to be examined is selected.
- ✓ A situation that represents the theme in question is prepared.
- ✓ Instructions are produced for the different roles in the situation – characters with specific functions, pre-determined behaviours, reactions, and positions.
- ✓ The situation that will be acted out is presented to all those taking part in the activity. The instructions and general information about the task are handed out.
- ✓ Each actor is asked to play the part in the most realistic way possible and according to the particular instructions. The rest of the group makes up the audience and is asked to carefully observe and keep notes on the behaviour, reactions, and arguments of the different characters.
- ✓ When the play is over, the situation is evaluated from the notes made by the audience.

Recommendations

A simple role play is the best. The facilitator stops the simulation or roleplay when exercise comes to a natural end, when enough issues have been uncovered or when people want to stop. Participants volunteer and are never forced to play a role they are uncomfortable with. Participants need a few minutes to get into their roles.

Material needed

For onsite sessions, any documentation relating to the role play (information and instructions); enough space; any material required for the role-play; papers and pens to take notes.

For online sessions, information and instructions sent before the event; any useful digital tools to collect ideas; and if the number of participants is high, one should consider splitting the group in different virtual rooms to

facilitate game management.

Conceptual mapping (individually or in groups;)

In-person / online session

A conceptual map is used to visually demonstrate the thought process on a chosen subject and to record ideas and their associations. Conceptual mapping is a means of brainstorming and organising thoughts. It facilitates the visual demonstration of brainstorming; it stimulates the generation of ideas and it also allows the creative process to be written up and made available for all to view.

How it is used

- ✓ The map is a schematic drawing with multiple branches.
- ✓ It has a central theme that acts as a starting point, written in the middle, which is the idea that you want to expand or the problem you want to solve.
- ✓ Branches inspired by associations made by participants sprout from the centre. The branches comprise a key image or a key word.
- ✓ Topics of lesser importance are represented as twigs of the relevant branch.
- ✓ Each branch can lead to a flow of new ideas, which are written down as key words, symbols or pictures.
- ✓ As topics and sub-topics emerge, additional associations are made between ideas that aren't necessarily grouped together. These relationships will be noted by using additional lines and arrows.

Material needed

Flipchart and different coloured pens if working in groups; when working individually, one sheet of paper and pencils for onsite sessions.

For online sessions, one should use a dedicated online tool (e.g. Miro or Jamboard) where one can reproduce a 'virtual' conceptual map which can be filled out by participants or by the facilitator as long as ideas are generated.

Phillips 66 (more than 15 participants; at least 1 hour)

In-person / online session

The Phillips 66 method was developed to get suggestions, opinions, or information from a large group of people in a short period of time, while ensuring maximum participation.

How it is used

- ✓ A participant is set in charge of the overall process.
- ✓ An explanation of the task and the ultimate objective should be given to participants. A subject and a question/problem are formulated to which the groups have to respond.
- ✓ Participants are divided into groups of 4-5 people. Each group chooses: i) a coordinator whose job is to remind the rest of the group about the time limit and allow each member of the group to put forward

their ideas and ii) a secretary who takes notes and writes down any conclusions (It can be useful to establish the groups in advance of the workshop).

- ✓ Groups have 6 minutes to respond to a question. Then the group discusses what has been identified, analyses cause and develops possible solutions. The conclusion is recorded by the secretary.
- ✓ Afterwards all groups join and report back to all participants by presenting their proposed solutions. Each secretary briefly explains their group's conclusions and generated solutions.
- ✓ The secretaries' presentations are summarised on a displayboard.
- ✓ Discussion starts and a general conclusion is reached.

Recommendations

The question asked should be able to produce a list of answers. Groups can be given up to 15 minutes instead of 6; but if more time is given, there is a risk that a debate will start, instead of just gathering new opinions and information which is the main objective of this method.

Material needed

Flipchart or display board, pens, paper sheets, enough space for each group to discuss the subject without disturbing other groups.

Problem tree (at least 1 hour)

In-person / online session

Problem trees are used when complex problems need to be analysed. This method shows the causes and consequences of a problem and helps people identify the aspects that should be tackled to achieve significant change. A problem tree involves writing causes in a negative form. Reversing the problem tree, by replacing negative statements with positive, creates a **solution tree** where the root causes are turned into root solutions. A solution tree identifies means-end relationships as opposed to cause-effects. This provides an overview of the range of projects or interventions that need to occur to solve the core problem.

Fig. 5 – Example of problem tree

How it is used

- ✓ Problem tree analysis is best carried out in a small focus group of about six to eight people.

- ✓ Clearly formulate the problem(s) that have to be analysed.
- ✓ A central problem is identified and placed in the middle of the tree.
- ✓ Participants are encouraged to identify the causes of the focal problem. These causes are the roots of the tree.
- ✓ Once the causes or roots of the problem have been established, the consequences are identified and become the branches of the tree.
- ✓ The causes and consequences can be created on post-it notes or cards, so that they can be arranged in a cause-and-effect logic.
- ✓ When the task has been completed, the drawing is analysed, and a discussion is encouraged to establish whether the organisation of the cards corresponds effectively to the causes and consequences.

The heart of the exercise is the discussion, debate and dialogue that is generated as factors are arranged and re-arranged, often forming sub-dividing roots and branches (like a conceptual map). Participants should be given time to explain their feelings and reasoning and record related ideas and points that come up on separate flip chart paper under titles such as solutions, concerns, and decisions.

Materials needed

Cards, post-it notes, paper sheets, marker pens, display board, flipchart for onsite sessions.

Digital tools to gather feedback for online sessions.

Storytelling (two hours up to one working day)

Storytelling is a powerful technique that has been used for many years in co-creation activities. This method is generally used as a team building exercise and also as a problem-solving exercise, as it assists knowledge sharing, builds new understanding, generate new ideas and triggers people to actively participate. Storytelling has the potential to bring user-centred and divergent thinking to scientists or other professionals who may tend to focus on the technical aspects and to have an analytical mindset. Storytelling unlocks imagination for the storyteller and the audience; and helps to spark new ideas or perspectives. Stories connect to people's individual memories, allowing them to draw on personal experiences and emotions for story building and story interpretation, again moving away from rational analysis. Furthermore, stories are a universal means of communicating that brings empathy for users because they make concrete how a technology can be used in context and how a user would react to it.

The aspects that should be defined for each story prior to the storytelling session are the following:

- Title of story
- The teller
- The listeners
- The main topic that wants to be addressed

- Description of the story's characters including their attributes and roles
- The problem and the respective actions
- Possible solutions to the problem

How it is used

- ✓ Establish a theme for the storytelling workshop. It could have a specific focal point or focus on a range of themes. Participants pair up and share their stories.
- ✓ Participants interview their partners, and write down partner's stories, using a story template.
- ✓ Participants form new pairs in order to share their partner's stories to a larger group.
- ✓ Each group of participants report back to the whole group in plenary session.

Recommendations

During the storytelling objects or comic sketches can be used to trigger memories of specific experience as well as to create visual hooks. A variation in the story can be added by using a "what if" question and try to find a solution to newly emerged scenario.

Go round (at least 30 minutes)

In-person / online session

The facilitator asks a question and then everyone takes a turn to speak on that subject without interruption or comment from other people once everyone has had the chance to speak. Go rounds are useful for equalising participation and giving everyone some clear space to express their opinion. Allowing people to 'pass' means that no one feels put on the spot. To keep it focused clearly state what the purpose of the go round is and write the question on a flipchart where everyone can see it. Time limits must be set to ensure all participants have a say.

Ideastorms (at least 30 minutes)

In-person / online session

A tool for sparking creative thinking and helping to quickly gather a large number of ideas. Begin by stating the issue to be 'idea-stormed'. Ask people to call out all their ideas as fast as possible – without censoring them. Have one or two notetakers to write all ideas down. Structured thinking and organising can come afterwards.

Variation

An ideastorm is a useful variation of the ideastorm that increases the level of participation and gets the group physically moving. It also allows you to think of ideas around several different, but related, issues at once. In a roving ideastorm small groups each start at a different 'station' (a tabletop or wall space with a sheet of flipchart paper on it) and have a short ideastorm on that station's topic. You call time and they then move round the other stations ideastorming as they go. A short, well enforced time limit will keep the small groups moving from station to station and make this a dynamic experience.

Map-it (at least 2 hours)

In-person session

Map-it is a participatory mapping method, used to enable the visualisation of a process in an open and flexible manner. It uses a set of icons that allow participants of different backgrounds to equally participate in a co-creation process by clearly express themselves in a visual way. The method can be used for a variety of goals such as co-creation of ideas and evaluation of concepts. It is easier and more practical to implement this method in-person.

How it is used

- ✓ Set up a research question and establish a clear goal.
- ✓ Define a well-timed mapping scenario, in which the components of the research questions are brought to the surface.
- ✓ If there are more than 10 participants the group should be divided.
- ✓ Each group should have a presenter.
- ✓ Each group receives sticker sheets in a different colour.
- ✓ The moderator explains the context, goal, and research question of the mapping session.
- ✓ When each group has finished its map, the presenter of each group, in turns, moves and explains the map to another table which in turn offers feedback and adds to the map.
- ✓ At the end of the sessions, each presenter gives a five-minute summary of the conversation.

Recommendations

During the mapping session, each group needs a moderator who makes sure the mapping session runs smoothly. Summarise the maps and results in a text or a summary map as they would be a good background for a possible follow-up mapping session. The moderator should ensure that time limits are kept.

Materials used

MAP-it kit, pens, documentation material.

Online brainstorming / information gathering (30-40 minutes)

Online session

Considering that several IDEAHL partners might need to implement sessions digitally, additional free digital tools for ideas' generation and co-creation discussions are provided to help them identify the most suitable approach:

- Google's Jamboard: it is the most basic and simplest platform, which gives the possibility to create sticky notes and collaborate real-time as a joint group–. - <https://jamboard.google.com/>
- Mural: it has many functional templates for brainstorming (e.g. sticky notes, mind map, also a template for asynchronous). One can download the tool as an App or as an integration of Microsoft Teams -

<https://www.mural.co/templates>

- Miro: it has an extensive library for brainstorming and idea generation (e.g. idea parking, breakout room), usable as an extension in various video call platforms (Zoom, Teams, Meet) - <https://miro.com>
- Lucidspark: it is a virtual whiteboard to collaborate with anyone in real time (to brainstorm and roadmap in a visual workspace). It can be integrated with: Zoom, Teams, Webex, Drive - <https://lucidspark.com>
- Canva: it can provide pre-set and colourful graphics that might be used for certain co-creation games and actions - <https://www.canva.com>

5.8.3 METHODS FOR EVALUATION PHASE

In a final stage of each co-creation session, a prioritisation and validation of the generated concepts may be needed to identify the most promising co-created ideas and wrap-up the main results emerged from the creativity discussion. During the evaluation stage, the generated ideas shall be checked and jointly assessed about some predefined criteria. These criteria will be determined according to the session's objectives. In the framework of the evaluation phase for IDEAHL cocreation, facilitators are recommended to foresee some time at the end of each activity to reach a consensus on the final assessment of the generated concepts. They can also compare the generated results against the outcomes of the WP1 mapping on (d)HL literature, best practices, champions, and survivors.

A list of useful and commonly used methods for evaluating the co-creation concepts are described below.

Two dimension axis (10-20 minutes)

During this method, participants will place the co-created concepts on a two-dimensional axis that will represent their feasibility and their potential. Through an open discussion and after participants have reached consensus, they will place each concept on the two-dimensional axis.

Materials needed

Display board, flipchart, marker pens, post-it notes for onsite sessions.

Online display board for online sessions.

Predefined number of stickers or dots (10-20 minutes)

Dot voting is one of the simplest ways to reach an agreed solution. Each participant is given a number of stickers or dots (1-5 is the usual number). All the co-created ideas are listed on a (physical or virtual) display board/flipchart. Participants are then asked to cast their votes by sticking their stickers or making their dots by the item/idea that they consider to be the most important. If they have multiple dots/stickers they can have the choice of spending them all in one concept if they feel strongly about it or spreading them across a number of choices. Once all the votes are cast, a list of the items by their new rank is made.

Materials needed

Display board, flipchart, marker pens, stickers for onsite sessions.

Online display board with the possibility to add “virtual dots” for online sessions.

Voting system using a Likert scale (10-20 minutes)

A voting system using a Likert scale may be used for specific, more experienced target groups like healthcare professionals and if there is enough time. It is a ranking system where the participants grade each concept in terms of feasibility, potential, and correspondence to the identified users’ needs, using a 10 level Likert scale. It is a rather time-consuming method, but its results will be accepted by everyone.

Ranking (10-20 minutes)

This is an effective technique for using in small groups. The groups of participants are asked to rank the options or reduce them to three, within a certain time limit. Having a participant to act as a facilitator in each small group will help. It is also helpful to set out clear rules from the start such as time limit, parameters of evaluation, etc.

Plus-minus implications (15-30 minutes)

This tool can be used in the whole group, in small groups or individually. The facilitator writes the topic across the top of a large sheet of paper (or shared online document) and writes a plus sign, a minus sign and an “I” (which stands for Interesting). By starting with the plus the facilitator asks people to list anything that they feel to be positive about the topic and write these without comment around the plus sign. When everyone has had their say the facilitator shall move on to the minus sign and list everything that people feel to be more negative. Around the “I” sign everything that people find interesting shall be written, such as ideas that could be explored further, etc. Then, a debate will be created in which all participants will be able to give their point of view and understand each other’s.

Materials needed

Large sheet of paper / dashboard and pen for onsite sessions.

Online dashboard or simply a shared online document where to write for online sessions.

5.9 POTENTIAL RISKS & PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

Potential external bottlenecks might come out during the co-creation experience, and partners will need to be prepared to manage them properly and take corrective actions. In the table that follows main indicative risks that can emerge in the preparation of T2.3 co-creation activities or even during the event day have been outlined with respective actions for addressing them.

Undesirable Situation	How to prevent it	How to manage it
Difficulties to recruit the expected number of participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Plan the recruitment well in advance, foreseeing a range of tools and methods to ensure recruitment from different channels and sources ✓ Make use of direct contacts, strategic collaboration agreements with known partners and local leaders/multipliers to maximise reach-out 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Adapt/change methods if one or more are not working effectively ✓ Seek support from local leaders / multipliers ✓ Intensify direct contacts for stakeholder engagement ✓ Compensate targets among groups i.e., if one group is easier to engage than the other, seek to ensure higher numbers for that group to preventively compensate potential under presentation of the other.
Participants do not confirm <i>When participants do not confirm a sense of uncertainty develops during the preparation of the activity</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Make the invitations in the right way ✓ Make confirmation easy ✓ Keep in contact with interested participants ✓ Keep a reserve list 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Insist on confirmation ✓ Use the reserve list

<p>A suitable physical activity venue cannot be found</p> <p><i>It is possible that some logistical matters cannot be confirmed in a timely manner, and they will have to be done at the last minute</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Start the process well in advance ✓ Visit different places chosen using predefined criteria and recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Adapt to the circumstances: identify all the advantages the available venue has to offer and minimise the problems ✓ Reserve the venue which meets the most requirements for the activity to take place
<p>The participants who have enrolled do not arrive on time</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Take care with the invitation and the enrolment and confirmation processes ✓ Provide clear instructions and assistance for getting to the venue if the activity is physical ✓ Send the agenda beforehand ✓ Generate commitment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Postpone the opening session of the activity to allow time for people to arrive ✓ Start and decide at what stage it is no longer viable for late arrivals to join
<p>The participants fail to work with a proposed tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Explain the procedure clearly from the start ✓ Assist and support the participants at the whole time of the event/session ✓ Prepare alternative tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Present and explain the reason for this particular tool ✓ Remain calm: the tool is there to aid the workshop and should not be defended to the point of exhaustion ✓ Choose an alternative ✓ Change this tool for another if the group agrees
<p>The participants are passive</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Make sure that all participants feel free to express their opinion. Some of them may feel that they lack the necessary expertise and will be reluctant to share their ideas and perspectives ✓ Find out about the participants' interests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Propose working in smaller groups to increase participation ✓ Use tools and activities that encourage interaction ✓ Find out the reasons for the passive behaviour so that you can find the means of securing their participation

<p>The group appears tired</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Choose a comfortable place ✓ Use several exercises as energizers ✓ Plan some time for non-scheduled small breaks ✓ Keep sessions within time limits in order to ensure that the workshop ends on time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Propose activities to liven up the group and keep it alert ✓ Keep your sense of humour ✓ Have spontaneous breaks
<p>Aggressive behaviour of one participant towards another person in the activity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Agree rules for behaviour and interaction ✓ Identify possible conflicts in advance ✓ Watch the participants' body language ✓ Be neutral and avoid judging ideologies, values, and beliefs ✓ Be an example; treat everyone equally and in a friendly way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Talk to the parties involved, remind them of the wellbeing of the workshop and suggest a time to speak ✓ Look for assistance within the group

5.10 CO-CREATION FOLLOW-UP

5.10.1 PARTNER REPORTING

Once each co-creation event is finalised, an **individualised report** will be **drafted by the facilitator(s)**, who will include a summary of all the necessary information of the implemented activities, such as number of participants, the team and their roles, the methodology and material used, a description of all the different sessions and a list with all the co-created concepts. These reports should be ready max. **within 1 week after the end of each session**, and they will follow the following format, including the aspects below:

<p>Introduction:</p> <p>A part that will state the time and place of the co-creation activity's implementation, its objectives and a brief summary of its structure, proceedings and overall success. The event's agenda according to which the event unfolded.</p>
<p>Description of the participant groups: A description of the participant profile, invitation criteria and number of attendants.</p>
<p>Description of the activity's sessions, discussions, outcomes: A detailed description of the overall structure of each workshop phase including the process followed, methods used, people in charge of the phase, main remarks, and main outcomes of each session.</p>
<p>Description of the co-created concepts and ideas related to the research questions.</p>
<p>Results from the evaluation of the session, conclusions, and next steps.</p>
<p>Annexes if applicable (Background material, photos, videos, etc.)</p>

A template of the report will be facilitated by ISRAA to partners in February 2023.

The report will be stored by the relevant partners on the project Teams folder and Task 2.3 Leader ISRAA will be informed by email. On the project shared Teams folder, only the report and relevant annexes must be uploaded. The attendance sheet of the organised events and any other sensitive data of participants should not be shared at project level but be kept at the premises of each project partner, which should indicate only the number of people attending co-creation activities when compiling the dedicated report.

5.10.2 FOLLOW UP : QUESTIONNAIRE & CERTIFICATE

Optional satisfaction questionnaire

At the end of the co-creation process, the participants will be given an optional (fully anonymous) **satisfaction questionnaire** that will aim to assess the main aspects of the experience and to offer an overall evaluation of the activities implemented. These assessment questionnaires will be **adapted** according to the target group and will be **completely optional**. They will be translated into the different languages required by the partners, so that they can be fully understood by all stakeholders in case they are not fluent in English. Questionnaires will be distributed at the last co-creation activity organised by the partners to collect views and opinions on the co-creation process. The questionnaire's template will be produced by WP2

Leader CE and Task 2.3 Leader ISRAA in February 2023 and made available to partners in both Word and online formats.

Preferably, partners will be requested to collect questions via the online based version of the questionnaire to centralise replies. Paper-based questionnaire is also an option for those groups with low levels of digital literacy. If paper-based questionnaires are administrated, then the project partner in charge will need to transfer the collected replies to the online based version of the survey. The assessment intended via the questionnaire will aim to elicit information on:

- The structure and design of the activity;
- The methods, the tools and materials used;
- The style of the facilitators and the rest of the team;
- Meeting the predefined event's objectives;
- The level of interaction and enjoyment;
- Logistical aspects (e.g., activity planning & management).

The feedback will offer partners the chance to reflect on the co-creation experience and aspects that may be corrected for following activities with other target groups.

Certificate of participation

Partners are encouraged to hand out a certificate of participation to all target groups' representatives that have taken part to the IDEAHL co-creation activities. English templates for the certificates will be made available to partners.

5.11 CO-CREATION DISSEMINATION

IDEAHL, as any other EU-funded project, has the obligation to disseminate its activities and results. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that partners promote their co-creation events through their digital channels and the project's ones. For this reason, guidance for the **dissemination of co-creativities activities before, during and after each co-creation event** is provided.

Before the event [optional but recommended]

Whenever relevant, members of the IDEAHL consortium can publicise their upcoming events on their own institutional social media, websites, newsletters, etc. On social media, if they post news

related to IDEAHL co-creation, partners are requested to tag the project accounts.

Partners may also consider the preparation of press releases about the co-creation activities at local level through local press, TV or radio. Moreover, they can hand out project dissemination materials (brochure, poster, leaflet) to the general public for recruitment and/or later to registered participants before the event and even during the recruitment process. For any doubt on project promotional materials, partners shall refer to CEI – WP5 Leader of Dissemination.

At project level, CEI will be responsible to track posts in which the project is tagged and re-post them through the official IDEAHL social media accounts.

Furthermore, by the start of the co-creation phase CEI will ensure the development of a dedicated sub-page on ‘Co-creation news/events’ on the IDEAHL website, which will be updated as long as partners organise co-creation events.

During the event [mandatory]

Partners must take pictures and/or videos during the co-creation activities as a proof of the implemented events. Visual material will be included in the follow-up report to be completed by the facilitator. If partners do not want to reveal participants’ faces, they can take people back pictures or make their faces blurred. If for privacy reasons partners do not want to show participants at all, they can take pictures at the event facility, at the facilitators speaking, at the ideas / results generated (e.g., boards, post-it, posters). However, if participants have given their written consent to appear in images, it is recommended to take and share pictures with participants as these will look more attractive for dissemination purposes.

At the same time, if possible, there could be some ‘live’ dissemination of the activities on social media to be posted both through the accounts of the partner organisations and the ones of the project. If partners conduct live dissemination, they must remember to tag the social media accounts of the project to allow CEI to quickly and easily re-post the piece of news.

After the event [mandatory]

The follow-up will consist of dedicated compulsory activities both partners and WP5 Leader CEI will be responsible for:

Typology	Dissemination action
<i>Partners organising co-creation activities</i>	
Pictures & Info	Relevant pictures/videos of the events should be attached to the Report Template (see Section 4.6) as soon as possible after the event and in any case not later than 1 week after the event itself. This information will be used to create a dedicated news on the IDEAHL website.
Social media	Partners are requested to produce at least 1 post on their (relevant) social media for each co-creation activity organised and they <u>must tag the official IDEAHL social media accounts</u> . This will allow Leader of Dissemination to easily re-post the news. It is recommended that posts on social media by partners are published right after the event not to “lose momentum”.
Partners’ website	Partners will promote their co-creation activities by publishing at least 1 article on their websites during the whole co-creation period.
Media/press releases	Information on the co-creation experience of IDEAHL can further be disseminated also through local/regional media and/or press releases.
<i>CEI, supported by CE and ISRAA</i>	
Project website	A dedicated page on ‘Events’ news’ will be created on the IDEAHL website and updated upon each partner organises a co-creation event and provides pictures and information. This data will be retrieved by CEI from the completed Report Templates. ISRAA will be in charge of informing CEI every time there is a new report available.
Project social media	CEI will re-post the news created by partners on social media to ensure a multiplier effect.
Project newsletters	Updates on the progress of co-creation will be included in the periodic releases of the IDEAHL newsletters, when applicable.
Media/press releases	Efforts can be made to develop specific press releases at EU or national level.

6. SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN AND OTHER ONLINE ACTIONS (T2.4)

Under T2.4, a **social media campaign** and other online actions to complement T2.3 activities are expected to be conducted. The aim is to inform the general public and targeted organisations on the development of the IDEAHL project, the co-creation process, and the (d)HL EU Strategy, as well as to get feedback on that. Different actions are planned:

- **Calendar of posts** prepared by CE and shared by the project social media. Partners will be requested to re-share them (and translate them if needed) through their own channels;
- **Online-based EU survey** prepared by CE and shared by partners through their channels and their partners' channels;
- **Additional small co-creation exercises** organised by ISRAA and CE upon needs and results of the T2.3 co-creation process.

The sections below describe the plan and the timeline agreed for the implementation of T2.4 activities.

6.1 SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

Under T2.4, a **calendar of posts** will be foreseen with dedicated **hashtags**. The analysis of "hashtags" will provide an understanding of the perspective of EU citizens on different aspects such as accessibility of (d)HL initiatives, benefits, as well as on needs, obstacles, etc.

First, a traditional leaflet and poster campaign will be created. Consortium members must be able to participate or collaborate and help spread the message in their localities or territories. This campaign, in turn, will have content dissemination elements such as specific hashtags previously determined to arouse audience curiosity. In this way, interested users will additionally have access to structured online content related to the project. Keywords messages for the hashtags will be, among others: digital health literacy, digital tools, health and wellness management, person-centred care. Hashtag generators e.g., Sixtrix will be exploited to decide and create key hashtags to use.

In accordance with the leaflet and poster campaign, the calendari92sed content to be disseminated in all social networks and online media will be required to include a "concretely defined" hashtag in the description or written sections. Thus, it will be possible to unify the

intention of conveying the message to the target group and enable access to content related to the project for all stakeholders.

To massify the project’s objective, collaborations with **influencers** involved in the health and wellness sector (leaders in the field at international or national/regional levels) and patients with chronic diseases, relevant in social networks, will be considered, as well as key actors in the social, political, citizen, and academic spheres in the European Union. The disseminated message should be supported with the established hashtag for structured access to the content by online users. A preliminary list of influencers and public figures has been drafted and will be expanded with the support of WP5 Leader of Dissemination and partners. Influencers will be contacted and asked to voluntarily disseminate the IDEAHL project and re-share specific content to help spread its activities and Strategy co-design.

Steps to follow:

6.2 EU SURVEY

An **online survey** is planned under T2.4 to collect additional feedback on the EU (d)HL Strategy, to complement inputs from T2.3 traditional co-creation activities.

The survey will be prepared by WP2 Leader CE, in cooperation with Task 2.5 Leader CSPA, in April 2023. It will be **disseminated from May to July 2023**. To build the questionnaire, CE will use the **EU Survey** tool.

The survey will be short, easy to complete, and fully anonymous. It will ask targeted questions to help Task 2.5 Leader CSPA to deepen certain aspects related to (d)HL that might need to be considered for the development of the EU Strategy and the associated deliverable (D2.3).

A landing page will be designed to deploy the survey through social media and conventional media. This will be shared through a unique link, and the results will be managed in real time by those responsible for the task. It will also be disseminated through all partner's channels to consolidate the delivery of the message. Outreach to stakeholders will be ensured through dedicated social media posts on IDEAHL official channels, promotion in newsletters and on the project website. Moreover, each partner will be requested to disseminate the survey among their organisations' staffs, own contacts, and experts.

6.3 ADDITIONAL CO-CREATION EXERCISES

Additional small co-creation exercises and/or discussions may be promoted during the co-creation phase to complement feedback retrieved from the previously described activities. In particular, so far, it has been agreed to implement the following:

- **Promote 2 online co-creation exercises with the IDEAHL consortium, (d)HL experts, and external Advisory Board (AB) members for the development of the deliverable 2.3 – the IDEAHL EU (d)HL Strategy.** (d)HL experts and WP4 experts and representatives from the EC Services will be invited. The first workshop will be planned around May/June 2023, with the aim to present first ideas for the deliverable content. The second workshop will be organised at the beginning of September 2023 to present the almost finalised version of the deliverable to gather final feedback from worldwide/EU (d)HL experts and reach consensus on the EU (d)HL Strategy.
- In parallel to the online co-creation sessions, it is planned to **share specific written content (or sections) of the EU Strategy deliverable with a dedicated panel of (d)HL experts and national/regional policy makers** in connection with project partner organisations. These will include experts from WP1 mapping, Advisory Board and stakeholders that were previously engaged in the policy making event in Brussels in March 2023 and in the WP4 workshop on inclusion and ethics.

Additional online activities might be added upon WP2 progress and evolution in the following months.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable outlines IDEAHL's co-creation methodology for the planning and implementation of the project's co-creation activities.

First, the document provides theoretical background and baseline for the co-creation approach and the research questions to be posed to engaged stakeholders. It summarises the outcomes of T2.2 analysis to set the framework in relation to (d)HL barriers, areas of improvements, etc., which have helped to establish the list of research questions to be posed to stakeholders during the co-creation process.

Second, the deliverable provides tailored and detailed guidelines, a calendar of activities, and steps to be followed by the project partners to successfully execute the traditional co-creation actions in their countries in line with T2.3 of WP2.

Finally, the document puts forward the framework and timeline for the online co-creation and awareness raising actions planned under T2.4 of WP2, with a special focus on the social media campaign to promote (d)HL and retrieve additional stakeholders' feedback for the IDEAHL Strategy's development.

The main conclusion after the elaboration of this deliverable is that a sound methodology was needed to provide all partner organisations with a common framework, approach, and timeline for co-creation execution to ensure. According to this, the partners of the IDEAHL project have been provided, with this deliverable, with specific tools, suggestions, templates to execute expected activities effectively and timely.

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9. ANNEXES

Annex 1 - List of tools for the co-creation sessions

FILE-SHARING TOOLS			
Tool	Website	Description	Cost
Sharepoint	https://www.microsoft.com/es-es/microsoft-365/sharepoint/collaboration	SharePoint is a web-based, collaborative platform that integrates with Microsoft Office. It is a document management and storage system.	Can only be used as part of Office 365.
Microsoft Teams	https://www.microsoft.com/es-es/microsoft-teams/log-in	Teams is a collaboration tool that provides dispersed teams with the ability to work together and share information via a common space. It includes features like video conferences, document collaboration, one-on-one chat, team chat.	Can only be used as part of Office 365.
Dropbox (business)	https://www.dropbox.com/es	Dropbox allows to share your photos, docs, and videos.	Standard plan (5T of storage) for 10€ (user/month).
Google Drive	https://www.google.com/intl/es-es/drive/	Google Drive is a free cloud-based storage service that enables users to store and access files online. The service syncs stored documents, photos and more across all of the user's devices, including mobile devices, tablets and PCs.	Free basic plan.

INTERACTIVITY TOOLS			
Tool	Website	Description	Cost
Slido	https://www.slido.com/?experience_id=13-a	Q&A and polling platform for meetings and events	Basic for free. Advanced features from EUR 149 per event.
Mentimeter	https://www.mentimeter.com/es	Interactive presentations & meetings. Allows to get a real-time input from the audience with live polls, quizzes, word clouds, Q&As and more.	Free: Unlimited audience size and unlimited presentations. Basic: \$10/month. Unlimited questions per presentation.
Kahoot	https://kahoot.com/	From e-learning to interactive presentations, training and virtual events. Kahoot can be used with conferencing tools such as Zoom, Google Hangouts, Microsoft Teams and Slack.	Starts from €10/month (1 host, 20 participants).

COLLABORATIVE TOOLS			
Tool	Website	Description	Cost
Moodle	https://moodle.org/?lang=es	Moodle is a learning platform designed to provide educators, administrators and learners with a single robust, secure and integrated system to create personalised learning environments.	Free basic plan.
Miro	https://miro.com/es/	Online collaborative whiteboarding platform to bring teams together, anytime, anywhere. Brainstorming, mindmapping, strategy and planning.	Simple version (unlimited team members, 3 editable boards) for Free (1 team). Advanced option for 5 teams from \$8 per user /monthly
Jamboard	https://jamboard.google.com/	Jamboard is a digital whiteboard that lets you collaborate in real time using either the Jamboard device (a 55-inch digital whiteboard that works with G Suite services), web browser or mobile app.	Free basic plan.
Trello	https://trello.com/	Trello's boards, lists, and cards enable you to organise and prioritise your projects.	Free basic plan.
Samepage	https://samepage.io/login	Same page allows messaging, task management, real-time document collaboration. On a single desktop and mobile app.	Starts at \$8/month. Free version available.